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Modelling and control of LV multiport converters

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1 Executive Summary

The EU's commitment to net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 necessitates rapid deployment of power converter-interfaced devices in electric power systems. This includes renewable energy sources (RESs) and energy storage systems (ESSs) in distribution networks (DNs). Traditional two-port power converters often fail to meet demand profiles effectively, leading to significant voltage fluctuations during generation-demand imbalances, particularly in radial feeders.

Multiport Converters (MPCs) provide an effective solution by integrating multiple energy ports into a single aggregated hub, offering high controllability and efficient energy management across all ports while maintaining power quality and grid stability. MPCs can address DN challenges by reducing conversion stages, leading to cost-efficiency and higher power density. MPCs offer flexibility in selecting the number of ports and their characteristics (AC or DC), making them ideal energy hubs for connecting feeders, substations, RESs, and ESSs. Compared to conventional systems composed of multiple individual interfacing converters, MPCs provide lower system cost, reduced size, and higher power density. Advanced controllability, communication, and computational capabilities in MPCs support future smart grids by decentralizing decision-making processes, enabling rapid responses, and holistic control to enhance overall grid performance.

WP3 focuses on investigating and enabling MPCs in low-voltage (LV) DNs, addressing challenges such as developing efficient and compact circuit topologies for interfacing three-phase and single-phase AC systems with multiple DC ports. This will enhance converter efficiency, improve power density, and reduce component counts by minimizing conversion stages. Additionally, control and modulation constraints will be addressed to ensure Zero-Voltage-Switching (ZVS) and reduce passive reactive elements to boost power density. High-performance current and voltage control techniques will maintain control bandwidth and impedance passivity across all ports for frequency intervals of interest, reducing dynamic instability and transient oscillations in future distribution grids.

At the distribution level, DNs with significant penetration of renewable sources and various industrial loads require power electronics to facilitate the integration of renewables and ESSs, optimize network use, and connect loads at different voltage levels. Power-electronic solutions like ESOP, smart transformers, and MPCs enhance capacity, flexibility, and controllability in distribution grids. For residential areas, MPCs accommodate future connections of EVs and distributed renewable generation, improving load balance, voltages, and renewable capacity.

In household settings, MPCs link local RESs and ESSs with the distribution grid, supporting local energy storage systems and EVs. This enhances system efficiency and reduces

integration costs, optimizing energy management at the household level and contributing to the overall stability and efficiency of the distribution network.

This report, Deliverable 3.1 of the iPLUG project, overviews the work carried out within WP3 research activities on MPCs for LV applications. Key contributions include identifying research challenges for SOP converters and propose, introducing a passivity-oriented controller design framework for robust stability, proposing novel single-stage non-isolated MPCs for residential applications, and enhancing dynamic performance with non-linear control of the Y-converter.

2 Introduction

2.1 Background and Motivations

The ongoing climate emergency and the EU's commitment to achieving climate neutrality with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 are driving the rapid deployment of power converter-interfaced devices in electric power systems. This surge in the adoption of power converters for integrating renewable energy sources (RESs) and energy storage systems (ESSs) into distribution networks (DNs) introduces challenges that require innovative solutions to ensure efficient and optimal operation [1].

Conventional two-port power converters are not being fully utilized to their full potential due to their low correlation and lack of controllability with respect to demand profiles, especially on radial feeders that can experience significant voltage fluctuations during generation-demand imbalances [2]. Therefore, new concepts as Enhanced soft-open points (ESOPs) have been proposed to address this issue by linking adjacent radial feeders and any co-located RESs or ESSs, facilitating peak shaving and other grid support functions [3,4], thereby increasing low carbon utilization.

Additionally, the rise in DC systems, such as ESSs and electric vehicle chargers, necessitates multiple conversion stages, which affect system costs, space requirements, and efficiencies. Despite these challenges, the abundance of energy sources and sinks offers opportunities for energy aggregation. High converter density scenarios, such as residential and commercial buildings, can benefit from more efficient integration of energy devices, leading to optimized energy utilization.

Multiport power converters (MPCs) provide an effective solution for integrating multiple energy ports into a single aggregated hub [5]. These converters offer high controllability, enabling efficient energy management across all ports while maintaining local requirements such as power quality and grid stability. The unique features of MPCs suggest they could significantly address distribution network (DN) challenges by reducing the number of conversion stages compared to traditional AC and DC multiterminal converter solutions, potentially resulting in greater cost-efficiency and higher power density [6].

Additionally, MPCs offer enhanced flexibility in the selection of the number of ports and their characteristics (AC or DC), making it an ideal energy hub capable of connecting various feeders, substations, renewable energy sources, and energy storage systems. Compared to conventional systems composed of multiple individual interfacing converters, multiport converters provide advantages such as lower system cost, reduced size, and higher power density.

Another significant feature of MPCs is their advanced controllability, communication, and computational capabilities, which are set to play a pivotal role in future smart grids.

Figure 1: Representation of a Multiport converter interfacing various sources, loads and storages.

By decentralizing decision-making processes, MPCs reduce reliance on a centralized grid management entity, enabling both local and system-wide decision-making. This facilitates rapid responses and holistic control, enhancing overall grid performance [7, 8].

In terms of grid-friendly integration, MPCs provide localized actions to support power quality, grid stability, and service continuity. Simultaneously, they enable grid-wide control to optimize overall grid behaviour, including efficiency, balancing, and congestion management. By leveraging the inherent flexibility of MPCs, these actions aim to improve grid performance [9]. Furthermore, advanced controllers within MPCs will employ sophisticated techniques and be adaptive, allowing them to evolve and learn based on real-time grid conditions. This ensures maximum security, quality, and stability. This adaptive approach guarantees robustness and responsiveness in dynamic grid environments.

Given the discussed motivations for MPCs, the primary scope of Work Package 3 activities is to investigate and enable MPCs in low-voltage (LV) distribution networks (DNs), considering both the distribution level and household/residential scenarios. To adopt MPCs in LV DN, various challenges need to be addressed, including developing efficient and compact circuit topologies to interface three-phase and single-phase AC systems with multiple DC ports. This will enhance converter efficiency, improve power density, and reduce component counts by minimizing conversion stages. Additionally, addressing control and modulation constraints, ensuring Zero-Voltage-Switching (ZVS) under varying conditions, and reducing passive reactive elements to boost power density are essential. High-performance current

Figure 2: Multiport converter for distribution level scenario.

and voltage control techniques, such as oversampling and digital hysteresis modulation, will be employed to maintain control bandwidth and impedance passivity across all ports. These measures are crucial for reducing dynamic instability and transient oscillations in future distribution grids.

2.2 Scope of WP3 Research Activities

In distribution level scenario where DNs have a significant penetration of renewable sources such as solar PV and wind power plants, along with various industrial loads, electric vehicle charging stations, and energy storage units, power electronics play a vital role. They facilitate the integration of renewables and energy storage systems, optimize the use of the distribution network, and enable the connection of various loads at different voltage levels, both AC and DC. Several power-electronic solutions have been discussed in the literature for enhancing capacity, improving flexibility, and enhancing controllability in distribution grids. These solutions include ESOP, smart transformers, and multiport converters. Additionally, there is a growing interest in introducing multiport converters in residential areas to accommodate future connections of EVs and distributed renewable generation. For example, a multiport converter has the capability to interconnect two low-voltage (LV) lines in a region to improve the balance of loads, voltages, and renewable capacity.

for distribution-level MPCs, back-to-back voltage source converters (VSCs) have demonstrated superior performance at high power levels and have been widely reported in various industrial projects. Therefore, the topology evaluation of distribution-level MPCs is considered well-covered in the literature [10, 11]. Additionally, as shown for two-port VSCs, three-level and multi-level VSCs can potentially improve performance compared to two-level VSCs, and these findings can be readily extended to back-to-back VSCs [12, 13].

In household/residential settings, MPCs can play a pivotal role in linking local RESs and

Figure 3: Multiport converter for residential level scenario.

ESSs with the broader distribution grid. Additionally, multiple ports of the converter can be designed to support local energy storage systems and electric vehicles. Implementing MPCs in household installations offers substantial advantages, including enhanced system efficiency and reduced integration costs for renewable energy, EVs, and energy storage compared to traditional methods. This approach not only optimizes energy management at the household level but also contributes to the overall stability and efficiency of the distribution network, paving the way for more resilient and cost-effective energy solutions.

For household/residential scenario, The primary technical and scientific objectives are threefold: First, it aims to provide a detailed assessment and evaluation of MPCs in low-voltage (LV) applications compared to multiple converters. This will involve a comprehensive analysis of losses, volume, and optimization of semiconductor devices and passive elements, considering factors such as switching frequency and wide bandgap device technologies. Second, the project seeks to propose novel MPC topologies to overcome existing limitations, such as reliance on DC-link or magnetic coupling, restrictions on power exchange, and the presence of circulating currents. These novel topologies will aim for single-stage power conversion, enhanced efficiency, power density, and bidirectional power flow at all ports. Third, the project will focus on ensuring reliable and high-performance control of MPCs through advanced controllers, oversampling, and digital hysteresis modulation, addressing dynamic interactions and minimizing disturbances with other power electronics converters in distribution grids.

2.3 Interrelations with Other WPs in the iPlug Project

The activities of WP3 are organized to align with the outcomes of WP1, ensuring compliance with grid codes and standards, considering the defined KPIs for evaluating different converters, and adopting the case studies presented in WP1. The following case studies have been considered in WP3 activities: Case Study 2.2 for interconnection of LV feeders, Case Study 2.4 for LV residential areas, and Case Study 4 for smart home installations.

Considering the interrelation with WP2, the proposed control techniques for FRT and impedance passivity can be extended to the medium-voltage case studies addressed in WP2. Additionally, the evaluation studies presented in WP3 can provide valuable insights for topology evaluation and ranking in WP2. For WP4, the proposed converters in WP3 and the impedance passivity approach can be utilized in the grid-interaction studies undertaken in WP4.

2.4 Summary of Contributions in This Deliverable

2.4.1 Fault-ride through of MPCs for SOP Applications

The primary aim of this study is to identify the research challenges associated with soft open point (SOP) converters during abnormal conditions such as faults and voltage sags. The analysis will involve examining the behaviour of SOPs and applying standard requirements to case studies to define the converter's duties. The study will uncover challenges in meeting these duties based on current state-of-the-art technologies. To address low-voltage ride-through (LVRT) and fault ride-through (FRT) capabilities, two approaches are proposed: unified control logic and centralized DC voltage control. The unified control logic, presented in the figure below, ensures compliance with both low-voltage ride-through (LVRT) and fault ride-through (FRT) requirements. While LVRT specifically addresses the system's response to voltage sags, FRT covers a broader range of fault conditions. The proposed approach guarantees sustained connectivity during voltage sags, enhances reactive power support, and aims to improve reliability by reducing the risk of voltage collapse. This is achieved through maintaining DC voltage control even in the event of a master station failure. The study explores various scenarios, detailing the specific responses required based on the nature and characteristics of each voltage sag or fault. The centralized DC voltage control for non-isolated MPCs ensures adequate DC bus voltage regulation under both normal and fault conditions. The proposed control architecture, presented in the figure below, offers several advantages. Firstly, it provides a flexible solution that can be implemented for multiple ports. In contrast to droop control, which is also suitable for multiple ports but introduces DC voltage regulation errors, the proposed solution achieves accurate regulation. Unlike VMM and droop control, the new architecture achieves zero

Figure 4: WP1 case studies utilized in WP3 activities.

steady-state error in DC voltage regulation. While the master-slave approach can also achieve accurate regulation, it fails if the master port becomes unavailable, resulting in a loss of DC voltage controllability.

Additionally, the proposed control architecture is robust against AC faults. Ports unaffected by AC faults can maintain control functionalities without disconnecting the MPC. Although VMM and droop control are robust against AC faults, they do not ensure accurate DC voltage regulation.

The control structure's objectives vary based on the operating conditions. In normal operation, the port must ensure power flow exchange among the ports according to the desired power references and voltage regulation of the common DC bus. In the case of AC faults, the port must ensure AC fault-ride-through capability, remaining connected to the AC grid during faults and injecting support fault current. It must also ensure converter current saturation, so the ports operate within safe current limits. Additionally, DC bus voltage regulation must be maintained by the available ports, ensuring those not affected by the faults retain their control capabilities.

2.4.2 MIMO Admittance Passivity for Robust Stability of Grid-Connecting Converters

The MIMO Admittance Passivity approach introduces a passivity-oriented controller design framework for multiport grid-connecting converters, exemplified through a digital current-controlled buck converter. This approach examines how the all-port MIMO admittance passivity properties depend on various parameters of the current control loop at frequencies where the influence of outer loops is negligible. Multi-sampled pulse-width modulation (MS-PWM), previously known for enhancing the converter's output admittance passivity at high frequencies, is shown to improve the all-port MIMO admittance passivity, preventing high-frequency port-coupling induced instability.

Additionally, input-voltage feedforward-based damping impedance emulation, which enhances the converter's input admittance passivity, is explored as a strategy for improving all-port MIMO admittance passivity at lower frequencies. By combining MS-PWM and input-voltage feedforward, simultaneous enhancement of MIMO admittance passivity at both low and high frequencies is achieved. Furthermore, an alternative approach using an input-feedforward passivity index, based on the minimum eigenvalue positive semi-definiteness condition, is illustrated for characterizing MIMO admittance passivity.

2.4.3 Novel non-isolated MPCs for Residential Applications

Two novel single-stage non-isolated MPCs have been proposed to interface the three-phase AC grid with DC systems. These MPCs enable direct power sharing between DC systems,

minimizing dependence on the AC grid and enhancing the efficiency and power density of the power electronic interface compared to using multiple two-port converters. The motivations for the proposed converters include their single-stage power conversion across different ports, potentially leading to higher efficiency and power density. Furthermore, the absence of bulky intermediate DC-link capacitors and transformers in the proposed topology contributes to improved power density and reduced costs. Additionally, the proposed MPCs feature buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports, independent of the DC ports' voltage, providing the flexibility to directly interface with a wide range of DC systems.

The proposed converters build upon the two-port Y-converter, transforming it from a two-port configuration into a multi-port one capable of connecting multiple DC systems to a three-phase AC grid. In its original form, the two-port Y-converter comprised three four-switch buck-boost modules, as shown in the below figure. To develop the multi-port converter, the four-switch buck-boost converter is expanded into a six-switch buck-boost converter formed with a shared buck half-bridge and two boost half-bridges. This can be developed in a symmetric or asymmetric configuration. In the symmetric configuration, the extension from a four-switch to a six-switch buck-boost converter is applied to all three modules. In the asymmetric configuration, the extension is applied only to one of the modules.

The asymmetric multi-port Y-converter, denoted as AY-MPC, offers a reduced structure with fewer semiconductor devices and inductors compared to the symmetric multi-port Y-converter, denoted as Y-MPC. For the case study where the two DC systems have different power levels, the AY-MPC enables the integration of the lower power DC system into the three-phase IC with a minimum number of components, resulting in a simpler structure and compact size. However, a challenge in the AY-MPC is to maintain balanced AC-grid currents.

2.4.4 Non-linear Control of the Y-converter

A loss-free resistor hysteresis controller is proposed for the Y-converter as an alternative approach to the conventional linear controllers presented in the figure below. The motivation for employing loss-free resistor hysteresis controller over traditional linear controllers lies in its ability to significantly enhance the dynamic performance of power converters. Linear controllers, while widely used, often struggle with rapid transient responses and maintaining stability across a wide range of operating conditions due to their inherent reliance on fixed gain settings and limited bandwidth. In contrast, loss-free resistor hysteresis control dynamically adjusts the switching actions based on real-time system conditions, allowing for precise control of current and voltage with minimal delay. This method also im-

proves response times to transient events and maintains stable operation without the need for complex compensation networks. Additionally, hysteresis control inherently adapts to variations in load and supply conditions, providing a robust solution that enhances overall system reliability.

2.5 List of Publications

A set of relevant publications has been realized within WP3, as follows:

- M. D. Hernández, O. Esquius Mas, M. C. Mañe, E. Prieto Araujo and O. G. Bellmunt, "Fault Ride Through Control of Multiport Converter for Distribution Grids," 2022 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference Europe (ISGT-Europe), Novi Sad, Serbia, 2022, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ISGT-Europe54678.2022.9960596.
- A. Y. Farag, D. Biadene, P. Mattavelli and T. Younis, "Three-phase Four-wire Bidirectional Y-converter for an Enhanced Interface between the AC Grid and the Unipolar DC Microgrid," 2023 8th IEEE Workshop on the Electronic Grid (eGRID), Karlsruhe, Germany, 2023, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/eGrid58358.2023.10380894.
- R. Cvetanovic, I. Petric, P. Mattavelli and S. Buso, "MIMO Analysis of Port-Coupling Induced Destabilization of Interlinking DC-DC Converters," 2024 IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (APEC), Long Beach, CA, USA, 2024, pp. 2806-2813, doi: 10.1109/APEC48139.2024.10509432.
- K. A. A. Mohammed, P. Mattavelli, T. Caldognetto, D. Biadene and P. Magnone "Analysis of Low Voltage Ride Through Capability in Multiport Converters for Soft-Open Point Applications," ELECTRIMACS 2024, Castello de la Plana, Spain.
- A. Y. Farag, D. Biadene, T. Caldognetto and P. Mattavelli, "Enhancing DC Microgrids Integration with Three-Phase AC Grids Using Multiport Converters," 2024 Power Electronics, Machines and Drives 13th International Conference PEMD 2024, Nottingham, United Kingdom.
- A. Y. Farag, D. Biadene, P. Mattavelli and T. Younis, "Three-Phase Four-Wire Step-Down Modular Converter for an Enhanced Interlinking in Low-Voltage Hybrid AC/DC Microgrids," in IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics, vol. 5, pp. 634-647, 2024, doi: 10.1109/OJPEL.2024.3394548.
- A. Y. Farag, D. Biadene, T. Caldognetto and P. Mattavelli, "Multiport Y-Converter for Three-Phase AC Grid Integration with DC Systems," 2024 IEEE 15th International Symposium on Power Electronics for Distributed Generation Systems PEDG 2024, Luxembourg, 2024.

- A. Y. Farag, D. Biadene, T. Caldognetto and P. Mattavelli, "Asymmetric Multiport Y-Converter for Three-Phase AC Grid Integration with DC Microgrids," Submitted to the 2024 Energy Conversion Congress & Expo Europe (ECCE Europe) **(To be presented)**.
- R. Cvetanović, I. Z. Petrić, P. Mattavelli and S. Buso, "On the Applicability of SISO and MIMO Impedance-Based Stability Assessment of DC-DC Interlinking Converters," in IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics, vol. 39, no. 9, pp. 10768-10780, Sept. 2024, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2024.3403236.
- R. Cvetanović, I. Z. Petrić, P. Mattavelli and S. Buso, "All-Port MIMO Admittance Passivity for Robust Stability of DC-DC Interlinking Converters," in IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2024.3430560.
- A. Y. Farag, D. Biadene, T. Caldognetto and P. Mattavelli, "Single-Stage Non-Isolated Multiport Y-Converter for Three-Phase AC Grid Integration with the 400 V DC Microgrids," **Under review** IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics.
- M. D. Hernández, M. Cheah-Mane, R. Grino and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "Centralized DC voltage Control for a Multiport Converter in Distribution Grids," **Under review** in IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics.

3 Analysis of Low-voltage Ride-through Capability in Multiport Converter for Soft Open Points Applications

This section focuses on multiport converters as key devices for enhancing flexibility and optimizing existing infrastructure. Multiport converters are designed to facilitate enhanced power flow control on meshed networks and extended operation in case of faults. As an example of multiport converters, traditional SOPs are explored in this study, configured in a back-to-back (B2B) circuit. SOPs are investigated for their vulnerabilities, particularly in fault scenarios disrupting the converter responsible for regulating the dc link voltage, so FRT approach is required to handle this situation. Furthermore, LVRT requirements mandate the converter to remain connected during voltage sags, to prevent undesired tripping and provide reactive power support to the grid. To address these challenges, a unified control logic is proposed, devised to handle both LVRT requirements and FRT conditions. This approach ensures system connection during voltage sags and provides reactive power support to the grid. Simulation results presented in this section validate the effectiveness of the proposed unified control logic, discussing its significance in enhancing the reliability of distribution networks and meeting the LVRT requirements.

3.1 Low-voltage Ride-through Requirements in PV Grid-connected Systems

LVRT control strategies for grid-connected photovoltaic (PV) systems under abnormal conditions should encompass rapid voltage fault detection, determination of active and reactive current setpoints, and mitigation of overcurrent failures through current limitation [14]. The IEEE Std. 1547-2018 specifies LVRT requirements applicable to this scenario, outlining voltage ride-through criteria that mandate grid-tied inverters to remain operational for a specified duration during a grid fault. The voltage duration profile varies among countries, taking into account factors such as voltage drop depth, fault time, voltage recovery time, and final voltage magnitude [15].

3.1.1 Overview of Relevant Standards and Requirements

In situations with a high number of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), disconnecting them from the power grid can worsen the power system's conditions, leading to more severe issues like power outages [16]. To tackle this challenge and ensure grid reliability, network operators are facing difficulties, especially with the implementation of updated grid codes like IEEE Std. 1547-2018 [15]. These codes include voltage ride-through criteria, specifying that grid-tied DER inverters must remain operational for a certain duration during

a grid fault.

The voltage duration profile, as illustrated in Fig. 5, varies among countries concerning factors such as voltage drop depth, fault time, voltage recovery time, and final voltage magnitude [17]. Besides staying connected during grid faults, DERs may also contribute by injecting or absorbing reactive power to aid in grid voltage recovery. This contribution is quantified by the ratio of reactive current (I_Q) to rated current (I_N), as depicted in Fig. 6. The fundamental idea is similar to voltage regulation through reactive power control: DER inverters absorb reactive power during voltage surges and inject reactive power during voltage sags. The specific requirements for reactive power support, like the ratio of reactive current to voltage sag/swell and the maximum required reactive power, also vary from one country to another [17].

In the event of temporary voltage disturbances, the DER operates within a permissive operation region if the voltage on the phase with the least magnitude is applicable. In such cases, the DER is required to either maintain synchronism with the Area EPS without tripping or choose to cease energizing. Additionally, DERs may possess dynamic voltage support capability during both low-voltage ride-through and high-voltage ride-through situations. The utilization of this dynamic voltage support capability can occur during mandatory or permissive operation. Importantly, the DER is mandated to maintain synchronism with the Area EPS and offer dynamic voltage support during and after temporary voltage disturbances.

But in other standards (Denmark standards, Germany (E.ON) [18] standard and Chinese standard GB/T 19964-2012) [19], there are different requirements of reactive power support.

3.1.2 Overview of Voltage Sag Detection Techniques

In order to ensure compliance with the Low Voltage Ride Through (LVRT) requirements stipulated in standards [15], [18], or [19], the initial and pivotal step revolves around the accurate detection of voltage sags. Voltage sags, characterized by a temporary decrease in the grid voltage below the specified threshold, necessitate a proactive approach for corrective actions.

The scientific literature provides a wide array of techniques designed to identify these voltage sags, each method carrying its distinct advantages and limitations. These techniques span a spectrum, varying from being straightforward and intuitive to complex. Furthermore, they differ significantly in their response times.

Importantly, these ways of finding voltage sags are also different in dealing with complicated grid scenarios. Notably, these scenarios may encompass unbalanced voltage sags, where different phases of the voltage experience unequal disturbances; phase-angle shifts

Figure 5: Voltage ride through requirements.

Figure 6: Reactive current injection requirement.

Table 1: Voltage Sag Detection Techniques

Detection Technique	Detection Time
RMS-Based Approach	Up to 40 ms
Variants of rms (s-rms, m-rms, r-rms)	Half of One Cycle
Fast Fourier transform (FFT)	One Full Cycle
Reduced fast Fourier transform (RFFT)	Approximately 3 ms
Hybrid Structure Combining Instantaneous Sag Detector and rms Variation Detector	Within 2.0 ms
Decoupled Double Synchronous Reference Frame Phase-Locked Loop (DDSRF-PLL)	12 ms
Enhanced Phase-Locked Loop (EPLL)	80 ms
Moving Average Filter with Phase-Locked Loop (MAF-PLL)	20 ms
Harmonic Footprint Detection	Less than 1 ms

in the voltage waveform, which pose challenges for straightforward detection; and the presence of harmonics within the grid voltage, adding a layer of complexity to the identification process [20].

Therefore, it is crucial to choose a voltage sag detection approach carefully for this reason. In order to guarantee both the correct and dependable compliance with LVRT criteria as well as the timely identification of voltage sags.

Numerous methods exist for detecting voltage sags, each offering distinct features and suitability. The widely-used Root Mean Square (rms) approach, while providing consistent performance, can be relatively slow, taking 1 to 2 grid cycles (up to 40 ms) [21]. Variants of rms, such as s-rms, m-rms, and r-rms, aim to expedite detection, with some achieving it within half a cycle. Other methods, such as dq-transformation in conventional synchronous reference frame PLL (SRF-PLL) are available but can be affected if the grid voltages are distorted and contain harmonics [22]. Multiple methods such as Decoupled Double Synchronous Reference (DDSRF), Synchronous Reference Frame with Low Pass Filter (LSRF), Enhanced Phase-Locked Loop (EPLL), and Moving Average Filter (MAF) are used in order to improve voltage amplitude detection in various situations. [16]. Another approach combines an instantaneous sag detector with the rms variation detector, providing detection times within a 2 ms delay [23]. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is a basic tool for achieving harmonic estimates or figuring out harmonic amplitudes and phase angles including techniques like fast Fourier transform (FFT), reduced fast Fourier transform (RFFT), short-time Fourier transform (STFT), and wavelet transform (WT). Their detection times vary based on the specific approach. For instance, FFT typically takes at least one full cycle, while RFFT operates in approximately 3 ms [24]. Finally, there's a method that incorporates harmonic footprints into an intelligent algorithm for the swift detection and classification of power quality events, typically within a fraction of a millisecond [25]. Some of these techniques are organized and summarized in Table 1 according to their detection times to provide a convenient overview.

3.1.3 Overview of Active and Reactive Current Setpoints Update Approaches at Sag Conditions

In [26], the paper suggests a controller for a three-phase inverter in a photovoltaic (PV) system. This controller is designed to maintain the PV system at its maximum power point (MPP) during voltage sags by minimizing peak values in the currents injected into the grid. This reduction in peak currents is achieved through the injection of current harmonics.

Reactive power support plays a fundamental role in meeting the essential criteria for Low Voltage Ride-Through (LVRT) capability. It is imperative to ensure that reactive power support is provided to effectively maintain grid stability and voltage levels during challenging grid conditions [27].

The different standards such as [15], [18], or [19] specify the regulatory framework governing the provision of reactive and active power support to the grid during periods of voltage sag conditions. However, it's crucial to emphasize that regardless of the regulatory requirements, a critical consideration in all scenarios is to account for the converter's rated current to prevent the occurrence of overcurrent issues [14].

In [28], when a balanced fault occurs, the primary goal of this paper is to enable the inverter to stay connected. Additionally, it aims to absorb excess energy while injecting the necessary reactive power during different fault scenarios to meet standard requirements.

In [29], the primary focus of voltage support control is to prevent overvoltage and undervoltage at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) whenever feasible. To achieve this goal, a mix of positive and negative sequence reactive power can be introduced into an inductive grid to bolster the grid voltage.

In [14] a current reference generation method with the objective of mitigating oscillations in active power and DC-link voltage when faced with unbalanced faults. The control strategy's primary goal is to dampen oscillatory components within active power while allowing reactive power to oscillate at twice the grid frequency. The method outlined in this study ensures that PV inverters maintain sinusoidal current injection even in the presence of unbalanced grid faults, effectively constraining the injected currents to their rated values during fault conditions.

3.2 Role of SOPs in Distribution System

With the increasing integration of intermittent renewables and the rising demand for electricity, distribution networks are confronted with the challenge of accommodating higher power flows within their existing infrastructure. While traditional network reinforcement remains an option for expanding capacity, its drawbacks, including high costs and time-consuming implementation, make it an undesirable solution. Consequently, there is a need for innovative approaches to dynamically enhance the utilization of existing assets and redi-

rect power flows through less burdened circuits [30].

One approach involves interconnecting or meshing the conventional radial network, allowing power delivery through less heavily loaded feeders and thereby alleviating stress on overloaded ones. This configuration has gained recognition in the development plans of various Distribution Network Operators (DNOs) by closing Network Open Points (NOPs). However, implementing this solution requires more complex and expensive protection schemes.

An alternative solution, bridging the gap between radial and mesh operations, is the adoption of a flexible mesh configuration. This is achieved through the use of a power electronic-based device called a Soft Open Point (SOP), replacing NOPs. Unlike the simple open/close functionality of NOPs, an SOP offers several advanced features:

- Flexible control of active power exchange between connected feeders.
- Flexible manipulation (absorption and supply) of reactive power on both interface terminals.
- Immediate post-fault supply restoration to support isolated loads on a feeder through power transfer from an adjacent feeder.

Consequently, the SOP introduces greater flexibility to current distribution networks, aiming to release capacity on existing feeders and enhance efficiency, and service quality for customers.

3.3 Proposed Unified Control Logic for SOPs

In this section, a unified control logic is proposed to ensure both LVRT and FRT requirements are met. While both LVRT and FRT deal with the system's response to abnormal conditions, LVRT is specifically about voltage sags, whereas FRT encompasses a broader range of fault conditions. The proposed work ensures sustained connectivity during voltage sags and enhanced reactive power support, aiming to improve reliability and reduce the risk of voltage collapse by upholding dc voltage control in the case of a master station failure. Diverse scenarios are presented, examining how specific responses are warranted based on the nature and characteristics of the voltage sag or fault at hand.

In the scope of our current study, both the voltage source converters utilized are three-phase three-wire converters. The control is implemented in the α - β frame. As in [31], the controller consists of two parts: a hybrid controller for power and dc voltage control and an ac-side current controller. The hybrid controller can switch between active power control mode and dc voltage control mode according to the state of the VSC. The current controller can regulate the ac-side current of the VSC using proportional-resonance (PR) controllers. The controller operates in the α - β frame. Fig.7 shows the overall control

Table 2: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	value
Grid Voltage	$V_{LL,rms}$	400 V
Line frequency	f_L	50 Hz
Rated Apparent power	S_{rated}	300 kVA
Switching Frequency	f_{PWM}	10 kHz
Converter Inductor	L	4 mH
DC link capacitor	C_{dc}	30 mF

architecture. The controller parameters are designed using a simplified model of the VSC. The main objective is to achieve reliable dc voltage control and to implement precise power regulation within the SOP. Furthermore, to improve the system's response during power disturbances, a power feedforward loop is implemented at the voltage control loop's output. This feedforward loop integrates the power reference signal into the control scheme. The inner current loops are implemented using a proportional resonant (PR) compensator within the α - β frame [32]. The SOP under investigation shares the construction and the control structure illustrated in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, with the corresponding parameters detailed in Table 2. The investigated scenarios include voltage sag at the master's grid, voltage sag at the slave's grid, and zero voltage at the master's grid with voltage sag at slave's grid.

3.4 Simulation results

3.4.1 Scenario 1: Voltage Sag at the master converter terminals

Fig. 9 illustrates the outcomes of the simulation under a voltage sag scenario at the rectifier side, where the master converter is positioned. At instant 0.4 s, a voltage sag is applied at the master's side, causing the port voltages to equal 0.4 p.u. and 1 p.u. at the master and slave sides, respectively.

Given that the master's grid voltage exceeds the minimum threshold, the master converter seamlessly continues its role in regulating the dc link voltage. However, the reduction in the master's voltage prompts an increase in master current to uphold a consistent power transfer between the two ports of the SOP. To prevent an uncontrolled increase in output current, the control loop employs a saturation block, enforcing boundaries for both upper and lower current limits. Consequently, the power transferred to the feeder at the slave side surpasses that transferred from the master side, leading to a discharge of the dc link capacitor. To avoid this issue, the power transfer reference between the ports is adjusted to zero during the voltage sag, as depicted in Fig. 9(e). Consequently, the slave converter's current diminishes to zero, as depicted in Fig. 9(c).

A current reference is derived from the power reference signal exchanged between the

Figure 7: Comprehensive control architecture for a two-port soft open point (SOP).

Figure 8: Simplified flowchart of the logic to handle LVRT and FRT conditions.

two ports. This current reference is integrated into the output of the dc link voltage controller, enhancing the system’s ability to swiftly reach a steady state following power disturbances and update events, as demonstrated in Fig. 9(b).

In alignment with the IEEE Std. 1547-2018 [15], providing reactive power support to the grid during a sag is desirable for stability maintenance. In Fig. 9(e), it is evident that reactive power is supplied to the grid at the master side, with the maximum value of the delivered reactive power defined by the converter’s rated current, illustrated in Fig. 9(d). The imposed maximum current limit is steadfastly maintained at 612 A.

3.4.2 Scenario 2: Voltage Sag at the slave converter terminals

Fig. 10 shows the simulation results under a voltage sag scenario, this time occurring at the inverter side, designated as the slave converter. At 0.4 s, a voltage sag transpired at the slave’s side, adjusting the port voltages to 1 p.u. and 0.4 p.u. at the master and slave sides, respectively. As the voltage sag is at the slave’s side, the master converter persists in its role of regulating the dc link voltage. Under normal conditions, the slave converter governs the regulation of power transfer between the two ports. However, the decrease in the slave’s voltage prompts a surge in the slave’s current to uphold consistent power transfer. This surge, in case of need, is curtailed by limiting the current signals in the control loop using a saturation block in the simulation, enforcing boundaries for both upper and lower current limits. Consequently, at 0.4 s, the power transferred to the feeder at the slave side diminishes, falling below the power transferred to the dc link from the master side. The dc voltage controller requires time to rebalance the power, resulting in an overshoot in the dc link capacitor voltage, as depicted in Fig. 10(b).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 9: Voltage sag at the master’s grid (rectifier side). (a) Slave’s/master’s rms voltage. (b) dc link voltage. (c) Slave’s grid current. (d) Master’s grid current. (e) Phase active/reactive power.

To support reactive power on the grid at the slave side, the active power reference between the two ports is adjusted to zero during voltage sag. Reactive power is then supported instead, as shown in Fig. 10(e). Consequently, the master converter's current reduces to nearly zero, as indicated in Fig. 10(d). Fig. 10(e) and Fig. 10(c) highlight that, the maximum value of the supplied reactive power is constrained by the converter's rated current, with the maximum current limit steadfastly maintained at 612 A.

3.4.3 Scenario 3: zero voltage at master's grid with voltage sag at slave's grid

In Fig. 11, the master's voltage declines to zero at 0.4 s, while the slave voltage decreases to 0.2 p.u. In this scenario, if the master's voltage falls below the minimum threshold, regulating the dc link voltage with the master converter becomes infeasible. Hence, the slave converter assumes responsibility for managing the task during the voltage sag. Consequently, the master's priority signal S for dc link control is set to zero.

The active power reference between the two ports is set to zero. With the master's voltage at zero, the reactive power transfer to the master's grid becomes zero, while a constrained value remains for the slave's reactive power. This transfer of control from master to slave, combined with the active power adjustment, ensures stable dc link voltage regulation.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 10: Voltage sag at the slave’s grid (Inverter side). (a) Slave’s/master’s rms voltage. (b) DC link voltage. (c) Slave’s grid current. (d) Master’s grid current. (e) Phase active/reactive power.

(e)

Figure 11: Zero voltage at the master’s grid and voltage sag at the slave’s grid. (a) Slave’s/master’s rms voltage. (b) DC link voltage. (c) Slave’s grid current. (d) Master’s grid current. (e) Phase active/reactive power.

4 Centralized DC Voltage Control of Non-Isolated MPC for Soft Open Points Applications

Non-isolated MPCs typically have a dc bus to interconnect all the ports. Then, the dc bus voltage regulation is essential to ensure that all ports can remain connected and exchange power. In the literature, most of the dc voltage control strategies that can be used for MPCs have been presented for dc grid applications, especially in dc microgrids [33] and High Voltage Direct Current (HVdc) grids [34]. In this case, two port control structures are typically used: master-slave [34] and distributed dc voltage control [35]. A conventional master-slave strategy is presented in [36], where one ac-dc grid terminal controls the dc bus voltage and reactive power while the other terminal controls the active and reactive powers [36]. However, if an ac fault is located near the master terminal the dc grid voltage regulation is compromised. Consequently, robustness with ac faults and conventional master-slave configuration is not guaranteed. On the other hand, distributed dc voltage control strategies have been presented in the literature to overcome the master-slave control limitations [37,38]. In this case, the most used strategies are Voltage Margin Method (VMM) [37] and droop control [38]. VMM controls the dc voltage inside a defined margin [37]. However, in a dc grid, VMM may not ensure dc voltage regulation at the nominal value and in case of a large number of ports, the implementation is complex and may be unfeasible. Droop control consists of a dc voltage proportional controller, which modifies the power (measured at the ac or the dc part) [39] or the dc current [40]. Therefore, droop control can be implemented at various dc grid terminals to regulate dc voltage and share dc power or current among the terminals [41]. Despite this, notice that droop control still results in an error at the dc voltage magnitudes. Communications could improve the voltage regulation in dc grids [42], but total costs would increase.

In the particular case of MPCs with more than two ports, the design of dc voltage control is mainly focused on dc-dc port ports, since they are used for dc distribution grids [43]. In SOPs, controller solutions are similar to dc grids. Master-slave control is a widely used strategy [44], although the limitations inherent in dc grids persist. Distributed dc voltage control strategies such as droop control and VMM are also featured in SOPs [45,46], showing the same benefits and limitations as those observed with dc grids. The authors have presented a VMM for a non-isolated MPC with two ac ports and one dc port [47]. Although different control options have been proposed for SOPs and MPCs, solutions for N-port MPCs have not been presented in the literature.

This section presents a centralized dc voltage control for non-isolated MPCs to ensure adequate dc bus voltage regulation in normal and fault operation. The proposed control architecture has the following contributions:

- Flexible solution that can be implemented for multiple number of ports. In the literature, droop control is also adequate for multiple ports, but presents dc voltage regulation error.
- Accurate dc bus voltage regulation. In contrast to the VMM and the droop control, a zero steady-state error is obtained. The master-slave approach can also achieve accurate regulation, but in case that the master port is not available, dc voltage controllability is lost.
- Robust control architecture against ac faults. Remaining ports that are not affected by ac faults can maintain control functionalities without MPC disconnection. In the literature, VMM and droop control are also robust against ac faults, but without ensuring an accurate dc voltage regulation.

In normal operation, the centralized dc voltage control is designed based on linearized models and applying an optimization problem with H_∞ norm to obtain the control gains. In fault operation, the general control structure is modified to ensure dc voltage regulation in case of ac faults at any MPC terminal. The proposed dc voltage control is tested in a LV distribution system with two feeders, where MPCs with three and four ports are connected at the end of the feeders. Time-domain simulations in Matlab-Simulink are considered to validate the MPC control.

Figure 12: Example of MPC application in a LV grid.

4.1 Definition of the topology, modeling and control of building units

This section presents the MPC architecture used in this chapter and the required control structure for normal operation in the ac-dc and dc-dc ports. The topology studied is a non-isolated configuration with a common dc bus, where the ac ports are ac-dc ports and the dc ports are dc-dc ports or outputs of the dc bus. Fig. 12 shows an example of an LV grid with MPCs, where the MPC is employed to interconnect LV ac feeders and to interface with a dc grid.

The port representation is based on average models, i.e. without including the switching operation of the ports, which is enough to capture the dynamic response defined by the port control. Therefore, on the ac side, the converter ports are modelled with a three-phase controlled voltage source and a series RL system, where L represents the inductance of the filter and the transformer, and R represents the equivalent resistance. On the dc side, the port ports are modelled as a current source and a capacitor is included in the common dc bus. A three-port MPC is analysed in this deliverable (as seen in Fig. 13), but also a four-port MPC is tested in Section 4.4 to validate that the presented control structure can be used for a higher number of ports.

The objectives of the control structure presented in this deliverable depend on the operation conditions: normal and fault operation.

In normal operation, the port must ensure:

- Power flow exchange among the ports according to the desired power references.
- Voltage regulation of the common dc bus.

In case of ac faults, the port must ensure:

- ac fault-ride-through capability, i.e. remaining connected to the ac grid during faults and injecting support fault current.
- Converter current saturation, i.e. the ports operate within safe current limits.
- dc bus voltage regulation by the available ports, i.e. the ports that are not affected by the faults have to maintain their control capabilities.

Fig. 13 shows an example of the general control structure in a 3-ports port and the control details of ac-dc and dc-dc ports are presented in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15, respectively. The control architecture presented in Fig. 13 is valid for N-ports ports, where the additional ports can be also ac-dc and dc-dc ports.

The ac-dc port control is a cascaded control with a PLL, an active power control and an inner current control implemented in the qd reference frame. Also, a positive-negative

Figure 13: MPC control structure with a possible structure of 3-ports.

sequence control is considered to ensure proper operation for balanced and unbalanced faults. The qd positive and negative sequence components are obtained using a filter that approximates the Hilbert transformation [48]. The reference of the negative sequence currents is 0, as assumed in [49].

Figure 14: ac-dc port control.

The dc-dc port controller is a cascaded control as with ac-dc ports, considering only dc components.

The centralized control block regulates the dc voltage bus ensuring that all the ports have to give support proportionally to its nominal active power. Section 4.2 explains in depth the control scheme.

In the following subsections, the control structure and design of the control architectures required in ac-dc and dc-dc converters for normal operation are explained in more detail. For fault operation, the control structures have to be modified and a fault current injection

Figure 15: dc-dc port control.

block and saturations as observed in Fig. 14 are required, as described in Section 4.3.

4.1.1 Active Power Control

To control the active power both ac-dc and dc-dc ports apply a reference current calculation, obtaining i_q^{*+} and I_c^* as:

$$i_q^{*+} = \frac{2 P^*}{3 v_q}, I_c^* = \frac{P^*}{V_{dc}}. \tag{1}$$

where P^* is the reference powers obtained from the centralized control, v_q is the q-component of the ac voltage and V_{dc} is the dc voltage measurement.

4.1.2 Reactive Power Control

This controller is only used in the ac-dc ports. In normal operation, the reactive power control is based on a PI controller to ensure reference tracking. The PI controller output is the current reference i_d^{+*} . In fault operation, the PI control structure is combined with a fault current injection block and an anti-windup loop, as explained in Section 4.3.1. The PI controller design is based on the methods described in [50,51].

4.1.3 Inner Current Control

Inner current control is used in ac-dc and dc-dc ports. The dc-dc ports require a single PI controller for the dc current. It should be noted that the positive sequence current references will be saturated following the strategy defined in Section 4.3.2. Negative sequence current references are not saturated because are defined as 0. In ac-dc ports, the control structure used is a double-crossed scheme with PI controllers, 2 for the positive sequence and 2 for the negative sequence [49]. The structure and design of this control strategy are explained in more detail for ac-dc ports in [50,51]. For the dc-dc ports the applied design is equivalent to the ac-dc ports.

4.1.4 Phase-locked Loop (PLL)

It should be noted that the MPC is working in grid-following mode, consequently, a PLL is used to estimate the grid angle and synchronise the ports with the grid [52]. The structure

of the PLLs is a closed-loop system with a PI controller. In fault operation modifications are necessary, as mentioned in Section 4.3.3. The design of the PI controller is explained in [50].

4.2 Centralized dc Voltage Control

This section presents the details of the centralized dc bus voltage control, which is indicated in Fig. 13 and shown in detail in Fig. 16.

4.2.1 Control Structure

The presented control is based on a PI controller, where the active power reference output P_i^* is distributed to all controllable ports, i.e. ports that are connected through an ac-dc or dc-dc port, as shown in Fig. 16. The power distribution is defined based on the weighting parameters α_i , which represent the contribution of each port to the dc voltage regulation. Therefore, the dc voltage is considered as a scalar variable that represents the power balance of the whole MPC. The PI controller and α_i gains must be correctly tuned to ensure that in steady state, the active power references $P_{0,i}^*$ are tracked. The weighting parameters α_i should ensure the condition $\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \alpha_i = 1$, where $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is the port number of the MPC and N is the total number of ports. The active power references are saturated at the nominal power of each port. Besides, an anti-windup control is included in the PI controller in case the port powers are saturated [53, 54].

Figure 16: Scheme of centralized dc voltage control.

The α_i calculation is defined based on Algorithm 1. The code prioritizes the ports with dc power supply systems to maintain the dc bus voltage. When dc power supply systems are not available (e.g. due to device failure or low state of charge), the code considers the existence of faults. If there are no faults the code calculates the parameter directly

with the nominal active power of each port. On the other hand, when there is a fault, the calculation of the α_i parameter is based on the product between the voltage seen by each port and its nominal active power. In the specific scenario in which a deep fault affects all the ports, the code calculates the parameter as in the case where no faults exist.

Algorithm 1: Algorithm to obtain α_i

input : Available active power of the dc power supply system P_{dci} , nominal active power of the ports P_i , ac voltages at the ports V_i

output: Weighting parameters α_i

```

1 begin
2   if the dc power supply system is available then
3      $\alpha_i = \frac{|P_{dc,i}|}{\sum_{j=1}^M |P_{dc,i}|};$ 
4   else
5     if no faults exist or there is a port with  $V_i = 0$  then
6        $\alpha_i = \frac{|P_{N,i}|}{\sum_{j=1}^M |P_{N,i}|};$ 
7     if a fault exists then
8        $\alpha_i = \frac{|V_i| \cdot |P_{N,i}|}{\sum_{j=1}^N |V_j| \cdot |P_{N,i}|};$ 

```

As mentioned, Algorithm 1 design ensures that available dc power supply systems have priority to maintain dc bus voltage stability. The value of α_i is calculated in this case as

$$\alpha_i = \frac{|P_{dci}|}{\sum_{j=1}^{M_{dc}} |P_{dci}|}, \quad (2)$$

where P_{dci} is the active power of the i dc power supply system, and M_{dc} is the total number of available ports with dc supply.

On the other hand, ac faults are analysed if a dc power supply system connected to the common dc bus does not exist. When no faults exist or all the ports observe a deep fault ($V_i = 0$) the value of the α_i parameter of each port is

$$\alpha_i = \frac{|P_{N,i}|}{\sum_{j=1}^{M_f} |P_{N,i}|}, \quad (3)$$

where $P_{N,i}$ is the nominal active power of the port i , and M_f is the total number of ports.

When no faults exist and at least one port is far enough from a fault ($V_i \neq 0$), the value of α_i is

$$\alpha_i = \frac{|V_i| \cdot |P_{N,i}|}{\sum_{j=1}^M (|V_j| \cdot |P_{N,i}|)}, \quad (4)$$

where V_i is the voltage measurement of the port i and M the total number of ports.

The application of (4) ensures that the ports with the highest contribution on regulating the dc bus have the most available margin. Section 4.4 shows the functioning of Algorithm 1 in different operation conditions.

4.2.2 Controller Design

This section presents the design of the PI controller used in the centralized dc voltage control. The PI controller is designed for disturbance rejection against active power variations from the ports $P_{0,i}^*$. Therefore, the grid and the MPC (without the centralized control) are defined as the plant of the system. The output of the plant is the dc bus voltage, while the inputs are the active powers obtained from the centralized control P_i^* , the reactive power references Q_i^* , the grid voltage U_{TH} and the grid frequency ω . In contrast, the output is the dc bus voltage V_{dc} .

Linearized models valid around an equilibrium point are considered to simplify the design. The plant defines the dynamics of all the control structure except the PI controller of the centralized control and the α_i gains. All the inputs are defined as 0, except the active powers, which are calculated as shown in Fig. 17.

Figure 17: Model of the system created for the controller design.

To validate the model a 2-ports MPC is studied. With the validated linear plant, the controllability and the observability are checked using the methodology presented in [55] to ensure the design is possible. The complete linear model with the plant and the controller has 16 states, 8 inputs and 15 outputs. The implementation of the completed linearized model in Fig. 18 is validated against the non-linear model in two time-domain simulations as shown in Fig. 19. In this case, the PI controller parameters of the dc bus voltage control have been initially selected following a trial-and-error approach. Active power references, ΔP_1^* and ΔP_2^* , are modified 1 % of their nominal value in two different simulations.

The PI controller is tuned to regulate the dc voltage against active power variations from the ports. In addition, the following specifications are defined:

- Minimum damping ratio of $\sqrt{2}/2$.
- A settling time of at least 0.45 s.

Control System Tuner toolbox of Matlab-Simulink is a tool that solves an optimization to calculate the PI parameters that satisfy or at least best meet the defined specifications. So, it is used to obtain the controller parameters for the closed-loop system.

(a) Scenario 1: Port 1 changing active power reference P_0^* .

(b) Scenario 2: Port 2 changing active power reference P_1^* .

Figure 18: dc voltage comparison between linearized and non-linearized model with $K_p = 600$ and $K_i = 2500$.

An optimization problem with H_∞ norm is considered to calculate the PI controller parameters that satisfy the previous specifications. The solved problem is defined with hard and soft requirements. This work defines only one hard requirement, attenuating the disturbances (active power references $P_{0,i}^*$). Consequently, the solver only obtains solutions that accomplish the attenuation condition. The other requirements are defined as soft, therefore the solver will obtain the nearest possible result to the defined specifications. This problem is solved using the non-convex and non-smooth optimization algorithms described in [56, 57]. Also, the H_∞ norm of the linear model is computed using the Control System Toolbox of Matlab and the algorithm defined in [58]. Figure 19 displays the eigenvalues (closed-loop poles) of the closed-loop linear model system matrix with different defined specifications.

In Fig. 20 the dynamic responses of the obtained specifications are compared with the

Figure 19: Closed-loop poles w.r.t some specifications of the PI centralized controller.

trial and error (*T&E*) PI. The fastest dynamic response is observed when a settling time lower than 0.45 s is defined. The damping ratio specification does not have an important effect on the design, as two conjugated eigenvalues have a damping of 0.696 that is not affected by the centralized controller PI design. Therefore, the designed control has a settling time of 0.45 s and a damping ratio of 0.696.

Figure 20: V_{dc} dynamics with different PI specifications.

4.3 AC Fault-ride Through Control

This section presents the additional control blocks to ensure that the MPC can provide fault-ride-through (FRT) capability, i.e. the MPC remains connected during faults at the ac ports

while the other ports maintain normal operation. The modified elements are:

- Reactive power control block.
- Current references.
- PLL.
- Active power references.

Also, these modifications must ensure an adequate dynamic response, especially after the temporary ac faults are cleared. Reactive power control, Fault Current Injection and modified PLL have already been presented by the authors in another publication [47]. The faults are represented by a signal named *Fault*, which is assumed to have a delay of 10 ms.

4.3.1 Fault Current Injection and Reactive Power Control Modification

To maintain the stability of the system, current is injected during the faults. In the grid codes, no limitations in which current has to be injected are presented, although reactive current is normally used when faults have to be isolated [59]. Therefore, to ensure FRT capabilities reactive current is injected. The reactive control part has a sample and hold (S&H) block to freeze the value of the reactive current when a fault occurs, as Fig. 21 shows.

This frozen value is used in the Fault Current Injection block to calculate the value of the injection current according to the $i - v_g^{qd}$ characteristics. Such attributes are based on the following piece-wise function:

$$\begin{cases} v_g^{low} \leq v_g \leq v_g^{high} \rightarrow & i_{inj} = \Delta i \frac{v_g^{high} - v_g}{v_g^{high} - v_g^{low}} \\ v_g \leq v_g^{low} \rightarrow & i_{inj} = \Delta i \\ v_g \geq v_g^{high} \rightarrow & i_{inj} = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (5)$$

where i_{max} is the maximum port current (typically an overcurrent of 105-110% is considered), v_g is the ac grid voltage and v_g^{low} and v_g^{high} are the voltage limits to define the maximum and minimum current contributions. The reactive power block uses an anti-windup structure to ensure that after a fault the dynamics are not affected by the accumulated error of the PI.

4.3.2 Current Saturation Strategy

The outputs of the active and reactive power control blocks are the current values in qd^+ reference for each port, which have to be saturated to ensure that the applied current is

Figure 21: Reactive power control and Fault injection block.

always inside the capability of each port. The i_{qd}^- current references are always directly 0.

The current limit values i^{low} and i^{high} , shown in Fig. 21, are the maximum and minimum values the current references could achieve. i^{low} and i^{high} have to be lower or equal to i_{max} , as it is the limit of the port. If the total current equals i_{max} a strategy must be defined to decide which component (q or d) has priority. Therefore, the values for the prioritized and the non-prioritized currents are

$$-i_{max} \leq i_{pr} \leq i_{max}, \tag{6}$$

$$-\sqrt{i_{max}^2 - i_{pr}^2} \leq i_{non-pr} \leq \sqrt{i_{max}^2 - i_{pr}^2}. \tag{7}$$

In this deliverable, following the grid codes [60], the reactive current defined by the d component always has priority. However, when a fault is seen by all the ac-dc ports and no dc power supply systems are available, the less affected ac-dc port prioritizes the q component. Following this strategy, the stability of the dc bus is prioritized.

Grid codes and standards [60, 61] recommend that when the voltage seen by a port is lower than 30% of its nominal value, the port has to be disconnected. And, when the voltage is bigger than 35% of its nominal value, the reference currents are again the calculated values obtained with the control blocks. However, this work aims to demonstrate

that a proper control design is sufficient to ensure that the port can remain connected even with voltages close to zero. Therefore ports are not going to be disconnected, even if voltages are almost zero.

4.3.3 PLL Modification

In this work, the PLL is modified to avoid a loss of synchronization during a fault, as shown in Fig. 22.

Figure 22: Block diagram of the modified PLL.

The grid frequency is frozen during fault duration considering the fault detection signal. When a fault occurs the PLL cannot follow the grid angle. Therefore the large difference between the estimated and the real frequency of the grid produces big variations of the angle. When the fault ends, the synchronism between the converter and the grid could bring undesired dynamics or even a loss of synchronisation. Furthermore, an anti-windup control is added to ensure that dynamics are not affected by the accumulated error of the PI when the PLL frequency is frozen.

4.3.4 dc Voltage Control Modification

The active power reference values are defined as zero during a fault, to ensure that all the available current is used to maintain the dc bus stability. The active power reference value of each ac-dc port $P_{0,i}^*$ is zero, when *Fault* signal is active.

4.4 Impact of control strategies in abnormal conditions and ac faults

The normal and fault operation of the MPC is validated in a LV distribution grid. The studied system has two feeders with the MPC connected at the end of them and loads are not represented, as shown in Fig. 23. It should be mentioned that the centralized dc voltage control was validated in normal operation with an MPC connected to separated ac systems, instead of a common distribution grid. However, a common distribution grid is more challenging in terms of control. Balanced and unbalanced faults are studied, especially focusing on the

Table 3: Case study parameters

Parameter	Value
Nominal ac grid voltage, V_{ac-N}	400 V
Nominal port port power, S_{c-N}	300 kVA
Nominal dc bus voltage of MPC, V_{dc-N}	800 V
Short Circuit Ratio, SCR	10
ac-dc active power references, P_{1*}, P_{2*}	0.66 p.u., -0.66 p.u.
ac-dc reactive power references, Q_{1*}, Q_{2*}	0.33 p.u., -0.33 p.u.
dc voltage reference, V_{dc*}	1 p.u.
dc-dc active power reference, P_{3*}	-0.33 p.u.
dc load active power reference, P_{4*}	0.33 p.u.
Equivalent impedance, R_{eq}, L_{eq}	1 p.u., 2.58 e-4 p.u.
Grid impedance, R_g, L_g	$0.7R_{eq}, 0.7L_{eq}$
Feeder 1 impedance, R_1, L_1	$0.15R_{eq}, 0.15L_{eq}$
Feeder 2 impedance, R_2, L_2	$0.15R_{eq}, 0.15L_{eq}$
Transformer impedance, R_t, L_t	$0.15R_{eq}, 0.15L_{eq}$
Coupling impedance, R_l, L_l	0.01 p.u., 0.2 p.u.

scenarios where the ac ports connected to the distribution grid are affected by a common ac fault, which represents a critical situation as was also analyzed in [47].

Three scenarios have been studied in order to validate MPC operation in normal and fault conditions:

- Scenario 1: 3-port converter with two ac ports connected to the feeders and one dc port connected to a battery (Fig. 23a).
- Scenario 2: 4-port converter with two ac ports connected to the feeders, one dc port connected to a battery and one dc port connected to a dc load (Fig. 23b).
- Scenario 3: 3-port converter with two ac ports connected to the feeders and one dc port disconnected (Fig. 23a).

The faults could be near ac-dc ports (between the port and the line impedances (F_2)) or in the interconnection point of lines 1 and 2 (between transformer impedances and grid impedance (F_1)).

The three scenarios have been tested with the same conditions. The references of the active and reactive powers are changed 0.2 p.u. its initial value to validate that the controller is well-designed in normal operation. Two fault locations are studied: F_1 and F_2 . F_1 represents a fault far from ac ports, while F_2 is a fault near ac port 2 (T_2). Therefore, F_2 is a deep fault for port 2 (T_2) and a mid-range fault for port 1 (T_1). Testing of balanced and unbalanced faults ensures that the MPC structure presented in this deliverable is validated in any ac fault condition. Faults last 0.25 s in all the scenarios. The unbalanced faults

(a) Scenarios with 3-port MPC.

(b) Scenario with 4-port MPC.

Figure 23: Scenarios considered for MPC control validation.

shown in this work are between phase A and the ground (Type B) [62]. A time domain simulation is done with the following events:

- $t=1.5$ s variation of dc load power (Scenario 2) or battery disconnection (Scenario 3).
- $t=3$ s variation of MPC power.
- $t=3.5$ s application of balanced fault (F_1).
- $t=5$ s application of balanced fault (F_2).
- $t=6.5$ s application of unbalanced fault (F_1).

4.4.1 Scenario 1: 3-ports MPC with Battery

This scenario is the simplest one, as a battery maintains the dc voltage stability.

In this scenario, as the battery is available during all the simulations, the α_3 parameter of the dc port remains 1 following Algorithm 1. Therefore, the controller works as a master-slave strategy in which the dc port is the master port. In normal operation, the MPC follows the P and Q references at the ac ports and the battery from the dc port compensates the required P and regulates the dc voltage, as observed in Fig. 24 (period before 5 s). When the reference is changed the battery changes its active power, adapting its value to ensure stability of the dc voltage.

In the case of balanced fault F_1 (from 5 s to 5.2 s), the ac voltage in both ports is close to zero. The ac ports reduce the active power while injecting positive reactive current. Also, the battery keeps dc voltage regulation modifying the injected P. ac-dc ports prioritize the reactive current as the battery is available and inject the required active power. Reactive current saturates at its maximum value, however, as ac voltages are zero, reactive power is zero. Negative currents remain zero in steady state, except in the transients between normal and fault conditions, where negative currents present a disturbance due to the notch filter used for the sequence decoupling.

At 7 s a balanced fault occurs near port 2 (F_2). ac voltages show that port 2 has an ac voltage near 0, but port 1 has an ac voltage of almost 0.3 p.u.. As with F_1 , the battery maintains the dc bus stability. In this case, port 1 still has some voltage, so its reactive power is different from 0.

When the unbalanced fault at the interconnection point (F_1) occurs (9 s) the behaviour is equivalent to the case with the balanced fault. The positive ac peak voltage sag is 1/3 of its nominal value, as only 1 phase is lost. Furthermore, negative ac voltage appears due the unbalance. Active and reactive power show 100 Hz oscillations during the fault, as the negative reference currents are defined as 0 [62]. When a 3-port MPC with a charged battery is connected, it is concluded that the system behaves as designed.

Figure 24: Scenario 1 results.

4.4.2 Scenario 2: 4-ports MPC with Battery and dc Load

This scenario is presented to validate that the MPC control structure presented in this deliverable can be extended to N number of ports.

Fig. 25 shows that in this case, the results are as with Scenario 2. At 1.5 s the dc load active power is changed. Therefore, the only differences appear with the active power of the battery, due to the existence of the dc load. As a consequence of Algorithm 1, the dc load is isolated from the ac faults during all the tests.

Therefore, if dc available power supply systems exist, adding ports does not affect the normal and fault operation of the MPC.

4.4.3 Scenario 3: 3-ports MPC without Battery

In this scenario, the battery regulates the dc bus voltage during normal and fault operation. dc load consumes active power, so it cannot be considered a dc power supply system. Following Algorithm 1, the α_i parameter of the dc load is zero. In this way, the system ensures that active power is always maintained constant, therefore the dc load is isolated from ac faults. It should be noted that the battery must have sufficient available energy capacity.

In this scenario battery is available until 1.5 s, consequently ac-dc ports are responsible for maintaining the dc bus voltage constant. Fig. 26 shows that the α_i parameter of the battery is 1 until 1.5 s.

In normal operation without battery, both ac/dc ports follow the P and Q references, while controlling the dc voltage. Both ports are equal, consequently, the value of α_i is 0.5.

The most critical condition occurs at 5 s when a deep balanced fault near the common grid occurs (F_1). α_i parameter is 0.5 in both ports because both ports PCC have a voltage equal to 0. During the fault, the active current is prioritized in both ports as there are no dc exchange systems and the same ac voltage is seen (almost 0 V). The voltage V_{dc} cannot be controlled, but by prioritizing the active current in both ports the dc voltage reduction is limited as much as possible.

At 5 s, a deep balanced fault appears near port 2 (F_2). ac voltages are different in both ports, having port 1 a bigger value than port 2. Following Algorithm 1, port 1 has an α_i parameter of 1. During the fault, port 2 prioritizes the reactive current. In port 1 the active current is prioritized, so the necessary current is given to ensure the system's stability. All the remaining current is available for reactive current. Port 1 consumes reactive power during the fault near its nominal value, due to the remaining available reactive current of port 1. As with the other scenarios, negative currents are zero when the fault starts and ends.

When the unbalanced fault at the interconnection point (F_1) occurs at 6.5 s, the dc bus

Figure 25: Scenario 2 results.

Figure 26: Scenario 3 results.

voltage can be maintained by both ac-dc ports. In both cases, the ports prioritize the active current, which maintains the dc bus voltage stable. The remaining current is used as reactive current. As with the other scenarios, the negative sequence current is zero except at the beginning and end of the fault. The active and reactive powers during the fault oscillate again at 100 Hz. From the different tests, it is concluded that the controller is also validated in this scenario.

5 All-Port MIMO Admittance Passivity

Within the objectives of the I-Plug project's work package 3, this section explores passivity-based control design framework for ensuring robust stability of low-voltage multi-port interlinking (*grid-connecting*) converters.

5.1 Introduction

Stability is of great concern in contemporary, power electronics dominated distribution systems/grids [63–77]. For assessing the small-signal stability of a *grid-connected* converter, impedance-based method is typically applied at a point-of-connection (port) of interest [63–68]. For this, the converter and the grid, being the subsystems seen at each side of that port, can be represented by the Norton and the Thevenin equivalent circuit [63,65,66]. Stability can then be determined by applying the (generalized) Nyquist stability criterion to the product of the corresponding grid's *terminated* impedance and the converter's *terminated* admittance [63,65–67].

Relying on this, admittance passivity criterion was derived and has become widely applied for analyzing and preventing destabilizing interactions between the converter and the grid [69–77]. Assuming a passive grid's *terminated* impedance, this standardly used criterion imposes the passivity of the converter's *terminated* admittance at the considered port as a sufficient condition for system stability [69–73,75–77]. Nevertheless, to determine such admittance, information about termination at all other converter's ports is necessary [66,67,78,79], which may be unknown or variable, e.g., for a multi-port *grid-connecting* (interlinking) converter [78]. If the impact of termination [79] is relevant, passivation of the converter's *terminated* admittance cannot guarantee stability due to the possible destabilizing impact of port-coupling [66,78]. Another shortcoming of the standardly used admittance passivity criterion is that it is difficult to apply in grids with meshed (as opposed to radial) structures [66,80].

Though the unterminated modelling and measurement principles were established long-time ago [81–86], they have only recently started being applied to all-port (unterminated) impedance-based stability analysis [80,87,88] and the corresponding admittance passivity-oriented design [89,90]. Along this line, with an aim to overcome the above discussed limitations of the standardly used admittance passivity criterion, the all-port MIMO admittance passivity criterion for dc-dc converters is proposed in [89]. The criterion arises from the all-port MIMO impedance-based method [80], which assesses stability by applying the generalized Nyquist criterion to the product of the grid's *unterminated* MIMO impedance matrix and the converter's *unterminated* MIMO admittance matrix. Stemming from this and assuming a passive grid's *unterminated* MIMO impedance matrix, the all-port MIMO

admittance passivity criterion imposes passivity of the converter's *unterminated* MIMO admittance matrix as a sufficient condition for system stability. This admittance matrix characterizes the converter's small-signal dynamics under ideal termination and can be used as a building block for analyzing interconnection dynamics [81–86]. Thus, the all-port MIMO admittance passivity criterion allows to analyze the impact of the grid-connecting converter in a general case of an arbitrary (even meshed) termination.

The MIMO admittance passivity condition from [89] involves evaluating the positive semi-definiteness of the matrix obtained as one half of the sum of the converter's unterminated all-port MIMO admittance matrix and its complex conjugate transpose [91]. For this, the non-negativity of the resulting matrix's principal minors [92,93], termed MIMO admittance passivity properties, was evaluated in [89]. These properties were then used to predict the port-coupling induced instability of a current-controlled buck converter. However, this instability was not demonstrated experimentally and the methods for its prevention were not addressed in [89]. Furthermore, impact of different control loop parameters on the MIMO passivity properties was not examined.

With the methodology from [89] as a foundation, this report aims to fill in these gaps and present a generally applicable passivity-oriented controller design framework for multi-port *grid-connecting* converters, exemplified through a simple digital current-controlled buck converter. The dependence of its all-port MIMO admittance passivity properties on several current control loop's parameters is examined at frequencies where contribution of outer loops can be neglected. Based on this, multi-sampled pulse-width modulation (MS-PWM) [94–96], which has so far been known for enhancing only the converter's output (switched-node side) admittance passivity at high frequencies [75,76], is shown to be advantageous for enhancing also the converter's all-port MIMO admittance passivity. Consequently, its capability to prevent the high-frequency port-coupling induced instability is demonstrated in this report. As an example of the control strategy that can successfully enhance the all-port MIMO admittance passivity at lower frequencies, input-voltage feedforward-based damping impedance emulation from [74] is explored, which has so far been known for enhancing only the converter's input (dc-link side) admittance passivity [74]. Additionally, it is revealed in this report that, by combining MS-PWM and the input-voltage feedforward, the MIMO admittance passivity can be simultaneously enhanced at low- and high-frequencies. As an addendum, an alternative, input-feedforward passivity index-based approach for characterizing the MIMO admittance passivity is illustrated. It relies on the minimum eigenvalue-based positive semi-definiteness condition [92].

The rest of this section is organized as follows. Section 5.2 introduces the all-port MIMO admittance passivity criterion and the MIMO admittance passivity properties. Their impact on the stability in grid-connecting scenarios, as well as their dependence on the control

Figure 27: (a) The two-subsystem representation for the impedance-based stability analysis of the two-port grid-connecting (interlinking) converter; (b) small-signal representation of the system from (a); (c) the simplified equivalent representation of (b), featuring the all-port MIMO matrix notation. In (b) and (c) the converter’s control system’s reference perturbation \hat{r} is justifiably assumed to be zero (see footnote 1).

loop’s parameters is illustrated in Section 5.3. In Section 5.4, the passivity enhancement methods are proposed and verified using control hardware-in-the-loop (C-HIL) simulations. As an addendum, an alternative, input-feedforward passivity index-based approach for characterizing the MIMO admittance passivity is illustrated in Section 5.5.

5.2 All-Port MIMO Stability Analysis

5.2.1 MIMO Impedance-Based Method

To determine small-signal stability properties of a grid-connecting (interlinking) converter, such as one from Fig. 27(a), the all-port MIMO impedance based-method can be used, which is thoroughly analyzed in [80]. Its fundamental principles, that are relevant for the methodology presented in this report, are outlined below. The detailed derivations can be found in [80]. As an example, a two-port dc-dc converter from Fig. 27(a) is considered hereafter, but the methodology is directly applicable to multi-port dc-dc converters. Due to an added layer of complexity in small-signal modeling of systems with a time-varying operating point, ac-dc converters will be addressed in a separate work.

The MIMO impedance-based method relies on the equivalent small-signal s -domain representation shown in Fig. 27(b) [80]. It involves representing the converter via the unterminated MIMO admittance matrix $\mathbf{Y}(s)$

$$\mathbf{Y}(s) = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{11}(s) & Y_{12}(s) \\ Y_{21}(s) & Y_{22}(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where s is the complex variable of the Laplace transform, and

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{11}(s) &= \left. \frac{\hat{i}_1(s)}{\hat{v}_1(s)} \right|_{\hat{v}_2(s)=0}, & Y_{22}(s) &= \left. \frac{\hat{i}_2(s)}{\hat{v}_2(s)} \right|_{\hat{v}_1(s)=0}, \\ Y_{12}(s) &= \left. \frac{\hat{i}_1(s)}{\hat{v}_2(s)} \right|_{\hat{v}_1(s)=0}, & Y_{21}(s) &= \left. \frac{\hat{i}_2(s)}{\hat{v}_1(s)} \right|_{\hat{v}_2(s)=0}, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{i}_{1,2}(s)$, $\hat{v}_{1,2}(s)$ are Laplace transforms of small-signal perturbations of $i_{1,2}$, $v_{1,2}$ from Fig.1,27 (a). The expressions for $Y_{11}(s)$, $Y_{12}(s)$, $Y_{21}(s)$, and $Y_{22}(s)$ can be derived based on the small-signal model of the converter and its control system [97], which is addressed in Section 5.3.2.

The grid is represented by the Thevenin voltage sources $\hat{v}_{g1}(s)$ and $\hat{v}_{g2}(s)$ and the unterminated MIMO impedance matrix $\mathbf{Z}_g(s)$

$$\mathbf{Z}_g(s) = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{g11}(s) & Z_{g12}(s) \\ Z_{g21}(s) & Z_{g22}(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where Z_{g11} , Z_{g12} , Z_{g21} , and Z_{g22} are defined analogously to Y_{11} , Y_{12} , Y_{21} , and Y_{22} in (9). In case the system is not meshed, i.e., the ports of the converter under study are solely interconnected by the converter itself [80], the grid's impedance matrix becomes diagonal ($Z_{g12} = Z_{g21} = 0$).

According to Fig. 28(b), the following holds¹

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}(s) = (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{Y}(s) \mathbf{Z}_g(s))^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{v}}_g(s) \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix, $\hat{\mathbf{v}}(s) = [\hat{v}_1(s), \hat{v}_2(s)]^T$, $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_g(s) = [\hat{v}_{g1}(s), \hat{v}_{g2}(s)]^T$ and T is the transpose operator. Subsequently, the circuit from Fig. 27(b) can be represented in a compact form shown in Fig. 27(c). Then, assuming that the grid is standalone stable ($\hat{\mathbf{v}}_g(s)$ is stable), stability of the grid-connecting converter can be determined by applying the generalized Nyquist stability criterion to the minor-loop gain $\mathbf{L}(s) = \mathbf{Y}(s) \mathbf{Z}_g(s)$ [80].

5.2.2 MIMO Admittance Passivity Criterion

For determining a sufficient condition for the stability of the system from Fig. 27, the all-port MIMO admittance passivity criterion can be used, which is derived by applying the frequency-domain passivity theory principles [91] to (11). Namely, provided that the grid's unterminated all-port MIMO impedance matrix $\mathbf{Z}_g(s)$ is passive, a sufficient condition for the stability of the interconnected system is passivity of the converter's unterminated all-port

¹In (11) and in Fig. 27(b) and (c), the converter's control-system reference perturbation $\hat{r}(s)$, and, consequently, the Norton current sources that account for its impact [80], are assumed to be zero. If the closed-loop reference tracking system is stable under the ideally stiff grid (which is reasonable to assume), this $\hat{r}(s) = 0$ allows for analyzing stability properties related solely to the converter's interaction with the non-ideal grid [80].

MIMO admittance matrix $\mathbf{Y}(s)$. The transfer function matrix such as $\mathbf{Y}(s)$ is called passive if $\mathbf{Y}(s)$ is stable and

$$\mathbf{P}(j\omega) = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{Y}(j\omega) + \mathbf{Y}^H(j\omega)) \geq 0, \forall \omega \in \mathcal{R} \quad (12)$$

where H is the Hermitian (conjugate transpose) operator [91]. Note that, due to the desired power conversion and regulation capabilities, as well as the system delays, a converter can never dissipate energy at all frequencies [69, 70]. Thus, in practice, the passivity condition (12) is usually relaxed to a frequency range Ω that is critical for stability [69–74]. Though this may be ambiguous from the strict passivity theory principle point of view, it has proven sufficient in practical power electronics applications [69–74]. Although there is still no unique regulation that defines the range Ω , some examples of the limits imposed by system integrators or standards can be found in [98, 99]. Also, the range Ω can be determined as a set of frequencies where grid's anti-resonances (or high grid impedance magnitudes), are known to be present, or where control loops are known to introduce stability problems. Accordingly, instead of $\forall \omega \in \mathcal{R}$, $\forall \omega \in \Omega$ is considered in (12). For the presentation conciseness, this notation is omitted in the subsequent conditions (such as (13)-(15), (31)) that are derived from (12).

Inequality (12) can be evaluated via any of the approaches that are standardly used in linear algebra to determine positive-semidefiniteness of a matrix \mathbf{P} [92]. Hereafter, the approach that evaluates non-negativity of *all* its principal minors is used [93]. An alternative approach that evaluates non-negativity of its minimum eigenvalue, which corresponds to the input feedforward passivity index of $\mathbf{Y}(s)$, is addressed in the Section 5.5.

According to the principal minors-based approach, for 2x2 $\mathbf{Y}(s)$ given by (8), (12) is equivalent to

$$P_1(j\omega) \geq 0 \quad (13)$$

$$P_2(j\omega) \geq 0 \quad (14)$$

$$P_{12}(j\omega) \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

where

$$P_1(j\omega) = \text{Re}\{Y_{11}(j\omega)\} \quad (16)$$

$$P_2(j\omega) = \text{Re}\{Y_{22}(j\omega)\} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_{12}(j\omega) &= 2\text{Re}\{Y_{11}(j\omega)\}\text{Re}\{Y_{22}(j\omega)\} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2}\text{Re}\{Y_{12}(j\omega) + Y_{21}(j\omega)\}^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2}\text{Im}\{Y_{12}(j\omega) - Y_{21}(j\omega)\}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Figure 28: Block diagram the considered digital output current-controlled pulse-width-modulated two-level buck converter, used as an example of the grid-connecting converter from Fig. 27 (a).

Note that if the edge case $\mathbf{P} = 0$ is excluded, it is sufficient to evaluate only the *leading* principal minors of \mathbf{P} [93].

As for the physical meaning of the, so called, MIMO admittance passivity properties, P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} , according to (16) and (17), P_1 and P_2 represent the effective conductance of the converter’s input and output self admittances Y_{11} and Y_{22} , respectively. On the other hand, the coupling passivity property P_{12} is a mathematical term that, contrary to P_1 and P_2 , reflects passivity considering also the coupling between the converter’s ports, as, according to (18), it depends not only on Y_{11} and Y_{22} , but also on Y_{12} and Y_{21} . Thus, to take into account the risk for the port coupling-induced instability, evaluation of $P_{12}(j\omega)$ is vital in the frequency ranges where the coupling between the converter’s ports is pronounced (e.g., where $|Y_{12}(j\omega)Y_{21}(j\omega)|$ is relatively high).

5.3 MIMO Admittance Passivity Properties

This section exemplifies the use of the above introduced MIMO admittance passivity properties for analyzing stability and developing robust-stability oriented control methods for an interlinking converter in several grid-connecting scenarios.

5.3.1 Control System Under Study

To illustrate core principles without introducing unnecessary complexity, hereafter, a single-stage digital output current-controlled pulse-width-modulated two-level buck converter is considered. Nevertheless, the methodology from this report can be applied to other two-level and multi-level topologies, as well as other single- and multi-stage control system architectures. The block diagram of the considered control system is shown in Fig. 28(a) and described below.

The inductor current is sampled at the rate $f_s = \frac{1}{T_s} = N_s f_{pwm}$, where N_s is the multi-sampling factor and $f_{pwm} = \frac{1}{T_{pwm}}$ is the frequency of the triangular PWM carrier w . The (feedback) sampling instants are synchronized with w so that one of them always coincides with $w = 0$, while the others are equidistantly spaced across T_{pwm} . Without any non-idealities, this allows for the average current to be sampled when $N_s = 1$ or $N_s = 2$. To enhance noise immunity and/or modulator linearity [94, 96, 100], the sampled current may be processed by a digital filter $G_{fii}(z)$. Afterwards, in the case of multi-rate control strategies [94, 100], an example of which is discussed in Section 5.5, a rate change from f_s to $f_c = \frac{1}{T_c} = N_c f_{pwm}$ may be imposed, where N_c and f_c are the control update factor and frequency, respectively. In the case of single-rate control strategies, considered in Sections 5.3 and 5.4 as well as in one of the examples in Section 5.5, $N_c = N_s$ and the entire digital domain is executed at a single rate, determined by the feedback sampling frequency f_s . In either case, the control update instants are synchronized with w so that one of them always coincides with $w = 0$ while the others are equidistantly spaced across T_{pwm} .

The (filtered and/or decimated) feedback signal i_f is subtracted from the current reference i_{2r} and the resulting error signal is processed by the current controller. As an example [101], the proportional integral (PI) controller is used, whose z -domain transfer function using bilinear transformation is

$$G_c(z) = k_p + k_i T_c \frac{z}{z-1} \quad (19)$$

where z is the complex variable of \mathcal{Z} transform, $k_p = 2\pi f_{cr} L_c$ and $k_i = 2\pi 0.1 f_{cr} k_p$ are the proportional and integral gain, respectively, f_{cr} is the crossover frequency of the current control loop, and L_c is the inductance of the buck converter's output filter. The gain k_p is set to achieve the desired f_{cr} , while k_i is set so that the impact of the integral action is limited well-below f_{cr} . If, with the goal of enhancing the converter's admittance passivity, it is of interest to emulate the damping impedance at the dc-link (input) port, which is addressed in Section 5.4.2, a positive "feedforward" action ("FF") of the converter's input voltage² may

²This can be considered as a feedforward action only in case the converter, without any input filter, is supplied from the grid with zero impedance ($Z_{g11} = Z_{g12} = 0$ in Fig. 27(b)), as only in this case \hat{v}_1 from Fig. 27 can be considered as an external disturbance. Otherwise, such an action should strictly be classified as a feedback. Still, it is in the literature most often referred to as feedforward [74]. Thus, to avoid misinterpretation, the term

Figure 29: Small-signal s -domain representation of the system from Fig. 28.

be added to the output of the main, feedback, current controller [74]. The “feedforward” action is obtained by processing the difference between the sampled converter’s input voltage v_s and the dc value V_1 of the input voltage v_1 through $G_{ff}(z)$, whose specific structure is addressed in Section 5.4.2.

The overall control action m_s , which is scaled to the range $[0,1]$ and may be delayed due to a finite control algorithm computation time [101], is forwarded to the digital pulse-width modulator. Within it, the impulse train $m_s[k]$ is held constant over one T_c to obtain the continuous-time modulating signal $m(t)$. Intersections between m and w define the switching signal $x(t)$, which is the square waveform whose steady-state duty cycle D determines the converter’s conversion ratio. Note that, for $N_c > 2$, a proper logic is implemented to prevent multiple-switching and pulse-skipping, that, unless properly handled, can arise when intersections between m and w are vertical (as opposed to horizontal) [94].

As for the modulator, two different PWM types are considered, distinguished based on the value of N_c . For $N_c = 2$ the standardly used double-sampled PWM (DS-PWM) is obtained, where the control update is performed at peaks and valleys of the triangular carrier w [101]. For $N_c > 2$, the multi-sampled PWM (MS-PWM) is obtained, where the control update is performed multiple times per modulation period [94–96]. Motivation for using MS-PWM arises from its inherent capability to reduce digital delays [94,95], which can be seen from the modulator’s pulse-to-continuous s -domain representation

$$G_{pwm}(s) = \frac{\hat{d}(s)}{\hat{m}(s)} \approx e^{-s \frac{T_{pwm}}{2N_c}} \quad (20)$$

where $\hat{m}(s)$ and $\hat{d}(s)$ are, respectively, Laplace transforms of the small-signal components of the continuous-time modulating signal $m(t)$ and duty cycle $d(t)$ of $x(t)$, used in averaged modeling [95,101]. According to (20), the higher the control-update factor N_c , the lower the modulation delay. Consequently, by reducing modulation delay [95,101], MS-PWM can enhance control loop’s dynamic performance, as well as high-frequency admittance passivity, which is addressed in Sections 5.4.1, 5.4.3 and 5.5.

feedforward will be kept in this report, but denoted by “” to emphasize ambiguity.

5.3.2 Small-Signal s-Domain Representation

The small-signal s -domain representation of the system from Fig. 28 is shown in Fig. 29. According to it, (9) yields

$$Y_{11}(s) = \frac{1}{1+T(s)} \left(-\frac{DI_{2r}T(s)}{V_1} + G_l(s)D^2 + G_{ff}(s)G_{pwm}(s) \left(G_l(s)D + \frac{I_{2r}}{V_1} \right) \right) \quad (21)$$

$$Y_{22}(s) = \frac{G_l(s)}{1+T(s)} \quad (22)$$

$$Y_{12}(s) = \frac{1}{1+T(s)} \left(-DG_l(s) + \frac{I_{2r}}{V_1}T(s) \right) \quad (23)$$

$$Y_{21}(s) = -\frac{G_l(s)}{1+T(s)} (D + G_{ff}(s)G_{pwm}(s)) \quad (24)$$

where $T(s) = G_c(s)G_{pwm}(s)G_l(s)G_{fil}(s)$ is the loop-gain of the reference tracking system. Further, $G_c(s)$, $G_{fil}(s)$, $G_{ff}(s)$ are the s -domain representations of the current controller $G_c(z)$, feedback filter $G_{fil}(z)$ and the “feedforward” action $G_{ff}(z)$. Finally, $G_l(s) = \frac{1}{sL_c + R_{L_c}}$, where R_{L_c} is the output filter inductor’s parasitic resistance, $I_{2r} = -I_2$ is the output dc current reference, V_1 and I_2 are the steady-state values of v_1 and i_2 , respectively. The delay due to finite computation time [101] can be included within $G_c(s)$ and $G_{ff}(s)$.

5.3.3 C-HIL Frequency Response Measurements

As a prerequisite for the subsequent passivity-based stability analysis, this section presents C-HIL frequency domain validation of the small-signal model discussed in Section 5.3.2. For this, the simplest variant of the control system from Fig. 28, which involves a single-rate control with DS-PWM ($N_s = N_c = 2$) with neither the feedback filters ($G_{fil} = 1$) nor the “feedforward” action ($G_{ff} = 0$) is considered. The parameters of the buck converter under study and its control loop are given in Table I. The corresponding MIMO admittance passivity properties are shown in Fig. 30, within the frequency range from 10 Hz up to $f_{pwm} = 10$ kHz. Note that, in case of control system architectures that feature outer, slower, loops (such as droop control), the passivity properties preserve qualitative resemblance to those discussed hereafter *only* if the contribution of the outer loops is negligible in the considered frequency range, which is typical at high frequencies [70]. Research along the line of wide-band MIMO admittance passivity in presence of outer loops is left for future work.

The waveforms shown in Fig. 30 with full lines are obtained from the analytical model. For this, the parameters from Table I and $s = j\omega$ are substituted in (21)-(24) and $P_1(j\omega)$, $P_2(j\omega)$, $P_{12}(j\omega)$ are calculated based on (16), (17), and (18). The waveforms shown in

Figure 30: Underterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity properties (16), (17), (18) of the buck converter with parameters from Table I and single-rate control system from Fig. 28, with DS-PWM ($N_c = N_s = 2$), with neither feedback filters ($G_{fil} = 1$) nor “feedforward” action ($G_{ff} = 0$). The results obtained from C-HIL simulations (dots) and analytical model (full lines) are shown.

Fig. 30 with dot markers are obtained from the frequency response measurements of the C-HIL implementation of the system from Fig. 28. For this, the converter is emulated via Typhoon HIL 402, with the circuit solver time step of $0.5 \mu\text{s}$. The inductor current is acquired from the HIL’s analog output. The ADC, the current control and the DPWM are realized within B-Board PRO control platform from Imperix. To obtain $Y_{11}(j\omega)$, $Y_{12}(j\omega)$, $Y_{21}(j\omega)$, $Y_{22}(j\omega)$, and subsequently $P_1(j\omega)$, $P_2(j\omega)$, $P_{12}(j\omega)$, the series perturbation injection circuits were emulated in HIL, and the frequency responses of interest were obtained using HIL’s dedicated SCADA widget. As seen in Fig. 30, the results obtained in this way from C-HIL simulations and those obtained from the analytical model are in agreement.

5.3.4 Grid-Connecting Scenarios Under Study

With the goal of illustrating the use of the MIMO admittance-passivity properties P_1 , P_2 , P_{12} for predicting the risk for the instability of the considered converter in various grid-connecting scenarios, that is addressed in Section 5.3.5, this section briefly explains the three considered scenarios, which are shown in Fig. 31. A nonmeshed grid is assumed ($Z_{g12} = Z_{g21} = 0$), whose impedances Z_{g11} and/or Z_{g22} form parallel anti-resonance circuits.

In Fig. 31(a) and (b), the anti-resonance is present at a single port only and the grid is assumed to be ideally stiff at the other port. Such scenarios, which are standardly consid-

Table 4: Parameters of the buck converter used for C-HIL validations.

Parameter	label	value	unit
Input dc voltage	V_{g1}	120	V
Output dc voltage	V_{g2}	85	V
Output dc current	I_{2r}	20	A
Steady-state duty cycle	D	0.75	V
Filter inductance	L_c	1.5	mH
Filter inductor's resistance	R_{L_c}	0.25	Ω
Switching frequency	f_{pwm}	10	kHz
Dead time	t_{dt}	0.8	μs
Multi-sampling factor	$N_s = N_c$	{2, 4}	-
Sampling frequency	$f_s = f_c$	{20, 40}	kHz
Crossover frequency	f_{cr}	1.4	kHz
Phase margin	PM	{48, 66}	$^\circ$

ered [69, 70, 75, 102], represent the applications where the impact of the port-coupling on the stability is negligible. One such application is the high-frequency passivity analysis of grid-connected voltage source converters, where, with a high-enough dc-link capacitor, the impact of the dc-link dynamics on the ac-side dynamics can be neglected [75–77, 103]. In such cases, the stability of the grid-connecting converter can be simply predicted by evaluating passivity of the converter's unterminated admittance where the grid's anti-resonance is present. This involves evaluating (13) (or (14)) around f_{g1res} (or f_{g2res}).

Still, there are applications in which, to accurately predict the risk for the instability, the coupling between the ports must be accounted for [66, 78]. Then, as derived from the MIMO admittance passivity condition (12) in Section 5.2.2, it is not sufficient to evaluate only (13) or (14), but also (15) has to be evaluated to correctly account for the possibility of port-coupling induced instability. A scenario used in this report to represent such applications is shown in Fig. 31(c). There, the grid's impedance at both ports features the anti-resonance.

5.3.5 Passivity-Based Instability Risk Prediction

Next, by evaluating whether, in the frequency range critical for stability, P_1 , P_2 , P_{12} from Fig. 30 satisfy (13), (14), and (15), it was of interest to predict the risk for the instability of the considered converter in grid-connecting scenarios shown in Fig. 31. Along this line, it should be emphasized, that, since (12) (which is equivalent to (13), (14), and (15)) is only a sufficient, but not necessary condition for stability [91], the instability will not necessarily arise in case (13), (14), or (15) are not satisfied. For example, stable operation will be achieved if the net sum of what is in this report referred to as the converter's *damping* and the grid's *damping* is positive at the critical frequency [91, 104, 105]. Thereby, in the unterminated all-port MIMO sense, the converter's *damping* at the frequency ω can be defined as the minimum eigenvalue of $\mathbf{P}(j\omega)$ [91, 105]. As such, according to the analysis

Figure 31: Grid-connecting scenarios considered for analytical passivity-based instability risk predictions and C-HIL time domain stability tests. The grid features anti-resonance at (a) port 1, (b) port (2), (c) both ports. By opening the switches $sw_{1,2}$, the grid's damping around anti-resonant frequencies is reduced.

in Section 5.5, it represents the joint effect of P_1 , P_2 , P_{12} , and corresponds to the input feedforward passivity index of $\mathbf{Y}(s)$ at the frequency ω . Analogously, the grid's *damping* at the frequency ω can be defined as the minimum eigenvalue of $\mathbf{P}_g(j\omega) = 0.5(\mathbf{Z}_g(j\omega) + \mathbf{Z}_g^H(j\omega))$, which corresponds to the output feedback passivity index of $\mathbf{Z}_g(s)$ at the frequency ω [91, 105].

The strict mathematical formulation and a quantitative application of the above informally stated *all-port MIMO positive-net damping criterion* is left for future studies. To preserve intuitiveness and simplicity, the subsequent analysis will indicate the instability risk by commenting on the extent of the converter's (negative) *damping*, which is determined by P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} , and the grid's (positive) *damping* around the critical, i.e., the grid's anti-resonant frequencies. To maintain the mathematical rigour, stability assessment is, for all of the hereafter discussed scenarios and test cases, performed also using the MIMO impedance based method from Section 5.2.1, similar as in [80]. The results, which are all aligned with the corresponding time domain stability tests, are not shown due to space limitation.

The instability risk predictions in the grid connecting scenarios from Fig. 31 are discussed below for the two test cases, different in terms of the values of the grid's anti-resonant frequencies (f_{g1res} and f_{g2res}):

- Test case 1: $f'_{g1res} = 200$ Hz, $f'_{g2res} = 4800$ Hz

- Test case 2: $f''_{g1res} \approx f''_{g2res} = 2500$ Hz.

As seen from Fig. 30, where the grid's anti-resonant frequencies are plotted as gray dash-dotted vertical lines, in the test case 1, (13) is not satisfied around f'_{g1res} . Thus, provided that the grid's damping around f'_{g1res} is low enough, instability is expected to arise in the scenario from Fig. 31(a). The same holds for the scenario from Fig. 31(b), since (14) does not hold around f'_{g2res} . Consequently, given that the converter is prone to being destabilized when the grid features the anti-resonance at a single port only (the scenarios from Fig. 31(a) and (b)), it is also prone to being destabilized when the grid features the anti-resonances at both ports (the scenario from Fig. 31(c)). To verify these stability predictions, time domain stability tests of the circuits from Fig. 31 are performed using the above explained C-HIL implementation of the system from Fig. 28. By opening the switches $sw_{1,2}$, the grid's damping around anti-resonant frequencies is reduced, and the transient is triggered. For the grid's anti-resonances' parameters corresponding to the test case 1, the converter's input and output current and voltage waveforms in response to such a transient are shown in Fig. 32(a), (b) and (c) for the scenarios from Fig. 31(a), (b), and (c), respectively. As seen, the previously made passivity-based stability predictions are in agreement with the time domain stability tests. Furthermore, the frequencies of the resulting oscillations correspond to the grid's anti-resonant frequencies.

As for the test case 2, the following passivity-based stability predictions can be made based on the results from Fig. 30. Namely, since both (13) and (14) are satisfied around $f''_{g1res} \approx f''_{g2res}$, regardless of how low the grid's damping around $f''_{g1res} \approx f''_{g2res}$ is, the system should remain stable in the scenarios from Fig. 31(a) and (b). However, despite (13) and (14) being satisfied, given that (15) is not satisfied around $f''_{g1res} \approx f''_{g2res}$, the instability is expected to arise in the scenario from Fig. 31(c), once the grid's damping around $f''_{g1res} \approx f''_{g2res}$ is reduced below a certain value. To verify this, C-HIL time domain stability tests are performed, similarly as above. For the grid's anti-resonances' parameters corresponding to the test case 2, the converter's waveforms in response to the transients triggered by opening the switches $sw_{1,2}$ are shown in Fig. 33(a), (b), and (c) for the scenarios from Fig. 31(a), (b), and (c), respectively. As expected, the system remains stable in the scenarios when the grid features the anti-resonance at a single port only. On the contrary, in the scenario when the grid features the anti-resonances at both ports, the port-coupling induced instability arises. The risk for it was successfully predicted by the proposed, under-terminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity-based method. Note that, though such a risk could have also been predicted by evaluating the passivity of the terminated admittance at the port of interest, this, as explained in [89], requires having the information about the termination at the other port(s), which may not be available and can also significantly vary during grid operation.

Figure 32: Input and output current and voltage waveforms obtained from C-HIL simulations of the converter with the passivity properties from Fig. 30 (DS-PWM without the “feedforward”), operated in the grid-connecting scenarios from Fig. 31 with the grid’s anti-resonances’ parameters corresponding to the test case 1. The transient is triggered by opening sw_{12} from Fig. 31 at $t = 0$ s. The results in (a), (b) and (c) correspond to the scenarios from Fig. 31(a), (b) and (c).

5.3.6 Impact of Control Loop’s Parameters

To prevent the instabilities that may arise in the grid-connecting scenarios, such as those analyzed above, the MIMO admittance passivity properties should be enhanced in the frequency ranges critical for stability. Along this line, it is of interest to understand first what the MIMO admittance passivity properties depend on. In principle, these properties depend on all the parameters that figure out in Y_{11} - Y_{21} from (21)-(24). For the control system without the “feedforward” action, some of the parameters relevant for these dependencies are the current reference I_{2r} , the duty cycle D , the control loop’s crossover frequency f_{cr} and the total delay τ_D present in the control loop, which can be due to modulation, computation, sensing and driving circuits, filters, etc. [101]. In this section, the dependence of

Test case 2

Figure 33: Input and output current and voltage waveforms obtained from C-HIL simulations of the converter with the passivity properties from Fig. 30 (DS-PWM without the “feedforward”), operated in the grid-connecting scenarios from Fig. 31 with the grid’s anti-resonances’ parameters corresponding to the test case 2. The transient is triggered by opening $sw_{1,2}$ from Fig. 31 at $t = 0$ s. The results in (a), (b) and (c) correspond to the scenarios from Fig. 31(a), (b) and (c).

the converter’s all-port MIMO admittance passivity properties P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} on the last two of these parameters (f_{cr} and τ_D) is investigated. For this, a simplified s -domain representation of the system from Fig. 28 without the “feedforward” action is used. It involves representing all the elements that introduce the delay in the control loop as a lumped delay τ_D in the direct path. Using the above described simplified analytical model, the passivity properties (16), (17), and (18) are calculated for different values of f_{cr} and τ_D .

First, the crossover frequency is swept from $0.05f_{pwm}$ to $0.2f_{pwm}$, while the delay is kept constant at $\tau_D = \frac{3}{2} \frac{T_{pwm}}{2}$. This value of τ_D is adopted as it corresponds to the standardly used single-rate control (without digital feedback filters) that involves DS-PWM and one-step computational delay. The other relevant parameters are the same as in Table I. The results for P_1 , P_2 , P_{12} are shown in Fig. 34(a), (b), and (c), respectively. As can be seen, the

Figure 34: The passivity properties (a) P_1 , (b) P_2 , and (c) P_{12} of the current-controlled buck converter from Fig. 28 ($G_{ff} = 0$) as a function of the control loop's crossover frequency (for a fixed $\tau_D = \frac{3}{4}T_{pwm}$). The results are obtained from the simplified s -domain analytical model, which involves representing all the delay elements as a lumped delay τ_D in the direct path.

width of the first, low-frequency, active region of P_1 is lower for lower values of f_{cr} , which is a well-known property of the converter's negative input resistance behavior [68]. The negative dip of the second, high-frequency, active region of P_1 is also lower for lower values of f_{cr} . The same holds for the negative dip of the high-frequency active region of P_2 , which is in agreement with the results from [75]. As for the impact of f_{cr} on P_{12} , reduction of f_{cr} reduces the width of the active region. The high-frequency negative dip is also reduced. Still, the low-frequency negative dip starts to arise for very low values of f_{cr} . Overall, according to the above outlined remarks, reduction of f_{cr} , i.e., control loop's bandwidth, can be considered beneficial for enhancing converter's all-port MIMO admittance passivity. However, by reducing f_{cr} , the control loop's primary function, i.e., regulation capability, is degraded, which can be acceptable only in some applications and only up to a certain extent. Thus, alternative methods for enhancing all-port MIMO admittance passivity should be investigated, which is addressed in Section 5.4.

To illustrate dependence of the converter's passivity properties on the delay, τ_D is swept from³ 0 to T_{pwm} , while the crossover frequency is kept constant at $f_{cr} = 0.14f_{pwm}$, which yields a 48° phase margin for DS-PWM with one step computation delay. The other relevant parameters are the same as in Table I. The results for P_1 , P_2 , P_{12} are shown in Fig. 35(a), (b), and (c), respectively. As seen, τ_D has negligible impact at lower frequencies, while it significantly impacts the high frequency passivity. By reducing τ_D , the width of the first active region of P_1 is increased. Nevertheless, the second active region of P_1 can be completely eliminated by reducing τ_D . The same holds for the high-frequency active region of P_2 , which is a well-known property of the converter's output admittance [76, 106]. Reduction of τ_D has positive impact on the coupling passivity property P_{12} as well, since its negative dip is reduced. Given all of the above mentioned, it can be concluded that the delay reduction enhances high-frequency all-port MIMO admittance-passivity. Furthermore, the delay reduction is also beneficial from the control loop's dynamic performance point-of-view, since, for the same crossover frequency, the lower delay yields the higher phase margin [94, 95]. This delay reduction is effectively obtained using MS-PWM, as addressed in the following section.

5.4 Methods for Enhancing All-Port MIMO Admittance Passivity

5.4.1 Multi-Sampled Pulse-Width Modulation

The positive impact of MS-PWM on the high-frequency passivity of the converter's output admittance Y_{22} , which is described by P_2 , is well-documented in the literature [76, 106]. Nevertheless, its positive impact on the converter's unterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity has not been reported before. To illustrate this, the system from Fig. 28 that involves a single-rate control with MS-PWM ($N_c = N_s = 4$) with neither the feedback filters nor the "feedforward" action is considered. The parameters from Table I are used. The passivity properties P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} of such a system are plotted in Fig. 36. As before, the frequency responses obtained from the analytical model (full lines) and C-HIL simulations (dotted markers) are shown, and, as seen, an excellent match between them is achieved. In addition, the analytically obtained passivity properties (shown with full lines in Fig. 30) corresponding to the previously analyzed system with DS-PWM are also shown (with dashed lines). As seen, by reducing digital delays, at high frequencies MS-PWM significantly reduces negativity of not only P_2 , but also P_1 and P_{12} . As such, MS-PWM can be considered beneficial for enhancing the converter's unterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity at high frequencies.

To further elaborate on this, the stability in the grid-connecting scenarios from Fig. 31 is

³Very low values of τ_D , which are close to 0, may be present in digital applications with MS-PWM, delay compensators (predictors), etc, as well as with analog control.

Figure 35: The passivity properties (a) P_1 , (b) P_2 , and (c) P_{12} of the current-controlled buck converter from Fig. 28 ($G_{ff} = 0$) as a function of the control loop's delay (for a fixed $f_{cr} = 0.14f_{pwm}$). The results are obtained from the simplified s -domain analytical model, which involves representing all the delay elements as a lumped delay τ_D in the direct path.

discussed next, considering the same test-cases and the grid's anti-resonances' parameters as in Section 5.3.5. Since, contrary to DS-PWM, with MS-PWM (14) is satisfied around f'_{g2res} , for the test case 1, the stability should be guaranteed in the scenario from Fig. 31(b). Furthermore, since, compared to DS-PWM, the coupling passivity property P_{12} is considerably enhanced with MS-PWM (its negative dip is lower) around $f''_{g1res} \approx f''_{g2res}$, for the test case 2, the system is less prone to getting destabilized in the scenario from Fig. 31(c). Then, provided that the grid's positive damping is higher than the converter's remaining negative damping around $f''_{g1res} \approx f''_{g2res}$, the port-coupling instability can be prevented. As for the rest of the scenarios and test cases from Section 5.3.5, stability with MS-PWM should remain the same as with DS-PWM.

To validate this, the time domain stability tests are performed using C-HIL, where the transient is triggered by reducing the grid's damping, as in Section 5.3.5. The plots of the converter waveforms in response to such transients are not included due to space limita-

Figure 36: Underterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity properties (16), (17), and (18) of the buck converter with parameters from Table I and single-rate control from Fig. 28 with MS-PWM ($N_c = N_s = 4$), with neither feedback filters ($G_{fil} = 1$) nor “feedforward” action ($G_{ff} = 0$). The results obtained from C-HIL simulation (dots) and analytical model (full lines) are shown. Dashed lines correspond to the analytical results from Fig. 30.

tions, but the overview of the results is provided in Table II. As seen, MS-PWM successfully prevents the high frequency instabilities that arise with DS-PWM, which is in agreement with the above discussed passivity-based stability predictions, derived from the proposed method. Not only is the instability caused by solely the interactions at the second port (test case 1, scenario from Fig. 31(b)) prevented by MS-PWM, but so is the port-coupling induced instability (test case 2, scenario from Fig. 31(c)).

Therefore, due to its capability to enhance the converter’s underterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity at high frequencies, MS-PWM can be considered very effective for preventing the converter’s high-frequency destabilizing interactions with the grid. Note that similar properties are expected with other low phase-delay modulators, such as double-sampled asymmetric dual-edge modulator [107]. Nevertheless, since the converter’s active behaviour at lower frequencies is not caused by the delays, digital delay reduction methods, on their own, do not have the capability to enhance the low-frequency passivity. For this, alternative methods are needed, one example of which is addressed below.

5.4.2 “Feedforward”-Based Damping Impedance Emulation

The positive “feedforward”-based damping impedance emulation has been proposed in [74] as an effective method for enhancing the converter’s input admittance in a bandlimited low-

Table 5: Overview of the control-hardware-in-the-loop time domain stability test results

test scenario	DS-PWM	MS-PWM	DS-PWM with “FF”	MS-PWM with “FF”	
test-case 1	f'_{g1res}	unstable	unstable	stable	stable
	f'_{g2res}	unstable	stable	unstable	stable
	f'_{g1res} & f'_{g2res}	unstable	unstable	unstable	stable
test-case 2	f''_{g1res}	stable	stable	stable	stable
	f''_{g2res}	stable	stable	stable	stable
	f''_{g1res} & f''_{g2res}	unstable	stable	unstable	stable

frequency range. The idea behind using the “feedforward” action, marked in gray color in Figs. 28 and 29, for emulating the damping impedance at the converter’s input can be explained as follows. According to (21), $Y_{11}(s)$ can be written as

$$Y_{11}(s) = Y_{11}^{noff}(s) + Y_{11}^{vi}(s) = Y_{11}^{noff}(s) + \frac{1}{Z_{vi}(s)} \quad (25)$$

where

$$Y_{11}^{noff}(s) = \frac{1}{1+T(s)} \left(-\frac{DI_{2r}T(s)}{V_1} + G_l(s)D^2 \right) \quad (26)$$

is the converter’s unterminated input admittance without the “feedforward” action, while

$$Y_{11}^{vi}(s) = \frac{G_{ff}(s)G_{pwm}(s)}{1+T(s)} \left(G_l(s)D + \frac{I_{2r}}{V_1} \right) \quad (27)$$

is the unterminated admittance’s part added by the “feedforward” action. Accordingly, the contribution of the input-voltage “feedforward” action can be seen as an additional parallel damping impedance Z_{vi} at the converter’s input port.

In the presence of non-zero grid’s impedance at the converter’s input port (such as Z_{g11}), the “feedforward” action may have the negative impact on the performance of the main feedback control loop [74]. To minimize this, it is of interest to choose $Z_{vi}(s)$ so that its impact is limited only within the narrow frequency range that is critical for stability [74]. As elaborated in [74], this can be achieved if the virtual damping impedance $Z_{vi}(s)$ exhibits the structure of the series RLC circuit

$$Z_{vi}(s) = R_{vi} + sL_{vi} + \frac{1}{sC_{vi}} \quad (28)$$

Figure 37: Underterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity properties (16), (17), and (18) of the buck converter with parameters from Table I and single-rate control from Fig. 28, without feedback filters ($G_{fil} = 1$), with DS-PWM ($N_c = N_s = 2$) and the “feedforward” action (from (29)). The results obtained from C-HIL simulations (dots) and analytical model (full lines) are shown. Dashed lines correspond to the analytical results from Fig. 30.

where R_{vi} , L_{vi} , and C_{vi} can be chosen to achieve the desired damping in the desired frequency range. This involves setting the appropriate values of the resonant frequency, quality factor and characteristic impedance [97] that the resonance formed by R_{vi} , L_{vi} , and C_{vi} shall satisfy. The “feedforward” action, through which the desired damping impedance $Z_{vi}(s)$ can be emulated, can be calculated from (27)

$$G_{ff}(s) = \frac{1 + G_c(s)G_l(s)}{\left(G_l(s)D + \frac{L_{2r}}{V_1}\right)Z_{vi}(s)}. \quad (29)$$

Along this line, a few aspects should be noted. First, to ensure the desired damping performance despite possible variation of D , L_{cI} , R_{cI} and other parameters, adaptive control may have to be employed. Second, all the delay-like elements (such as modulation, computation or feedback filtering) are neglected in (29), to make the practical realization of $G_{ff}(s)$ feasible. With such a virtual damping design approach, which is used in this report as an example, depending on the desired frequency range for the virtual damping impedance emulation (the resonant frequency of Z_{vi} from (28)), the emulated virtual damping impedance’s frequency response will differ from the desired one (described by (28)), to an extent determined by the amount of the delays present within the control

Figure 38: Underterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity properties (16), (17), and (18) of the buck converter with parameters from Table I and single-rate control from Fig. 28, without feedback filters ($G_{fil} = 1$), and with both MS-PWM ($N_c = N_s = 4$) and the “feedforward” action (from (29)). The results obtained from C-HIL simulations (dots) and analytical model (full lines) are shown. Dashed lines correspond to the analytical results from Fig. 30.

loop. Thus, unless combined with some delay reduction methods, the resonant frequency of Z_{vi} from (28) should be kept below frequencies where delays significantly change phase of the system. Next, unless combined with some online resonance detection algorithm and adaptive control [108], the “feedforward” method will be effective only if the frequency range where the damping is needed does not change significantly. Finally, for the implementation within a digital control system, $G_{ff}(s)$ should be discretized to obtain $G_{ff}(z)$, for which the pole-zero matching discretization method is used in this report.

Though reported as effective for enhancing passivity of the converter’s input admittance [74], the capabilities of the above described control method to enhance the converter’s underterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity have not been explored in the literature so far. Along this line it should be mentioned first that, since the “feedforward” action affects not only Y_{11} , but also Y_{21} , it impacts both P_1 and P_{12} . Still, according to (21) and (24), this impact is “of opposite sign”. Accordingly, though the lower R_{vi} always enhances P_1 , this does not necessarily hold for P_{12} . Thus, care has to be taken when designing the feedforward action to ensure enhancement of both P_1 and P_{12} . Research along this line is left for future.

As an example that illustrates the impact of the “feedforward” action on the all-port

MIMO admittance passivity, the system from Fig. 28 that involves a single-rate control with DS-PWM ($N_c = N_s = 2$) without feedback filters and with the “feedforward” action is considered. Same as before, the parameters of the converter and the main feedback current control loop from Table I are used. The “feedforward” action is designed so that the virtual damping impedance (28) ensures passivity of Y_{11} around f'_{g1res} , which corresponds to the standard input admittance passivity-oriented design [74].

The passivity properties P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} of such a system are plotted in Fig. 37. As before, the frequency responses obtained from the analytical model and C-HIL simulations are shown. In addition, the analytically obtained passivity properties corresponding to the system with DS-PWM and without the “feedforward” action (analyzed in Section 5.3.3) are also shown in Fig. 37, for comparison. As seen, the addition of the “feedforward” action enhances passivity around f'_{g1res} of not only P_1 , but also P_{12} .

To further elaborate on the impact of the “feedforward” action on the converter’s admittance passivity, the stability in the grid-connecting scenarios from Fig. 31 is discussed next, considering the same test-cases and the grid’s anti-resonances’ parameters as in Section 5.3.5. Contrary to DS-PWM without the “feedforward” action, for DS-PWM with the “feedforward” action, (13) is satisfied around f'_{g1res} . Thus, for the test case 1, stability should be guaranteed in the scenario from Fig. 31(a). However, by adding the “feedforward” action P_2 and P_{12} remain unaltered around f'_{g2res} and $f''_{g1res} \approx f''_{g2res}$, respectively. Therefore, same as the system with DS-PWM and without the “feedforward” (Section 5.3.3), the system with DS-PWM and the “feedforward” action is expected to be destabilized in the scenarios from Fig. 31(b) and (c), for test case 1, and in the scenario from Fig. 31(c), for test case 2.

To validate this, the time domain stability tests are performed using C-HIL, where the transient is triggered by reducing the grid’s damping, as in Section 5.3.5. The plots of the converter waveforms in response to such transients are not included due to space limitations, but the overview of the results is provided in Table II. As predicted, the addition of the input voltage “feedforward” action successfully prevents the instability from Fig. 32(a), which is caused by the low-frequency active region of Y_{11} . Nevertheless, as discussed above, the high-frequency destabilization issues from Fig. 32(b) and (c), as well as Fig. 33(c) are not solved by adding the input-voltage “feedforward” action (see Table II). This is because the “feedforward”-based damping impedance emulation is in the considered example intentionally designed as a low-frequency bandpass action (in this case around f'_{g1res}), to limit its negative impact on the main control loop and achieve the desired damping action in presence of non-negligible digital delays. Furthermore, this method does not alter Y_{22} at all, as seen from (22). Therefore, with the goal of enhancing the converter’s unterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity simultaneously at low- and high-frequencies, it

Figure 39: Input and output current and voltage waveforms obtained from C-HIL simulations of the converter with the passivity properties from Fig. 38 (MS-PWM with the “feedforward”), operated in the grid-connecting scenarios from Fig. 31 with the grid’s anti-resonances’ parameters corresponding to the test case 1. The transient is triggered by opening $sw_{1,2}$ from Fig. 31 at $t = 0$ s. The results in (a), (b) and (c) correspond to the scenarios from Fig. 31(a), (b) and (c).

may be of interest to combine the input voltage “feedforward”-based damping impedance emulation with other methods, like MS-PWM, which is addressed below.

5.4.3 Combination of MS-PWM and the “Feedforward”

In this subsection, the system from Fig. 28 that involves a single-rate control with MS-PWM ($N_c = N_s = 4$) without feedback filters and with the “feedforward” action is considered. Same as before, the parameters of the converter and the main feedback current control loop from Table I are used, while the parameters of the “feedforward” action are the same as in Section 5.4.2. The passivity properties P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} of such a system, obtained from the analytical model and C-HIL simulations, are plotted in Fig. 38, again benchmarked against the case of DS-PWM without the feedforward action. As seen, the “feedforward” action and the MS-PWM act independently, enhancing thereby the converter’s unterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity in the two distinct frequency ranges. The former contributes to

Figure 40: Input and output current and voltage waveforms obtained from C-HIL simulations of the converter with the passivity properties from Fig. 38 (MS-PWM with the “feedforward”), operated in the grid-connecting scenarios from Fig. 31 with the grid’s anti-resonances’ parameters corresponding to the test case 2. The transient is triggered by opening $sw_{1,2}$ from Fig. 31 at $t = 0$ s. The results in (a), (b) and (c) correspond to the scenarios from Fig. 31(a), (b) and (c).

P_1 and P_{12} becoming positive at low frequencies, specifically around f'_{g1res} for the considered design of the “feedforward” action. The latter contributes to improving P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} at high-frequencies (which includes f'_{g2res} and $f''_{g1res} \approx f''_{g2res}$). Thus, all the instabilities (from Figs. 32 and 33) that the system with DS-PWM and without the “feedforward” action was causing in the grid-connecting scenarios from Fig. 31 are expected to be successfully overcome by using MS-PWM and the “feedforward” action. To demonstrate this, time-domain stability tests using C-HIL are performed. The transient is triggered by reducing the grid’s damping, same as before.

The converter’s input and output current and voltage waveforms in response to such transients are shown in Figs. 39 and 40 for the test case 1 and 2, respectively. Compared to the results from Figs. 32 and 33, obtained for DS-PWM without the “feedforward” action, by using MS-PWM with the “feedforward” action, not only are the instabilities caused by, respectively, low- and high-frequency non-passive regions of Y_{11} and Y_{22} successfully

prevented, but so is the port-coupling induced instability. As seen from Table II, where an overview of all the previously discussed time-domain stability test results is provided, only by using both MS-PWM and the “feedforward” action is the stability ensured in all considered grid-connecting scenarios and test-cases. It is worth mentioning that, as opposed to the above discussed independent action of the MS-PWM and the “feedforward” in the two distinct frequency ranges, these methods can also be combined in a way to act jointly in the same frequency range (e.g., near or slightly above f_{cr}). Research along this line is left for future studies. Finally, depending on the properties of the grid under study, i.e., the frequency ranges where it exhibits (anti-)resonances, use of only one of the above discussed methods may be sufficient.

5.5 Input Feedforward Passivity Index-Based Analysis

Alternatively to evaluating the principal minors of $\mathbf{P}(j\omega)$, which is considered throughout the report, the eigenvalues of $\mathbf{P}(j\omega)$ can be evaluated to examine passivity of \mathbf{Y} [72, 92]. Namely, condition (12) is equivalent to all the eigenvalues of $\mathbf{P}(j\omega)$ (which are by definition real) being non-negative [92]. This is further equivalent to the smallest of the eigenvalues being non-negative. Accordingly, for \mathbf{Y} given by (8), the condition (12) is equivalent to

$$\lambda_{min}(j\omega) \geq 0 \quad (30)$$

where

$$\lambda_{min}(j\omega) = \frac{P_1(j\omega) + P_2(j\omega)}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{(P_1(j\omega) + P_2(j\omega))^2 - 2P_{12}(j\omega)}}{2}. \quad (31)$$

It is interesting to note that λ_{min} is in fact the input feedforward passivity index of $\mathbf{Y}(s)$ at the frequency ω [91, 105].

To illustrate the use of λ_{min} for characterizing the converter’s all-port MIMO admittance passivity, a few examples, previously addressed via the principal minors-based approach, are addressed below via the minimum eigenvalue-based approach. First, λ_{min} of the current controlled buck converter analyzed in Section 5.3.3 (featuring DS-PWM without the “feedforward” action) and Section 5.4.3 (featuring MS-PWM with the “feedforward” action) are plotted in Fig. 41. Same as before, the results obtained from the analytical model are plotted with full lines and those obtained from C-HIL simulations are shown with dotted markers. The results for λ_{min} shown in Fig. 41 in purple and green color correspond to those for P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} shown in Figs. 30 and 38, respectively. As can be seen, the reasoning about the converter’s MIMO admittance passivity that was made by evaluating P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} is in agreement the trends of λ_{min} .

Figure 41: Passivity property (31) of the buck converter with parameters from Table I and single-rate control system from Fig. 28 without feedback filters ($G_{fil} = 1$). The results shown in purple and green color correspond to those from Figs. 30 and 38, which are obtained for DS-PWM ($N_c = N_s = 2$) without the “feedforward” action and MS-PWM ($N_c = N_s = 4$) with the “feedforward” action, respectively. The results obtained from C-HIL simulations (dots) and analytical model (full lines) are shown.

Figure 42: Passivity property (31) of the current-controlled buck converter from Fig. 28 ($G_{ff} = 0$) as a function of (a) f_{cr} for $\tau_D = \frac{3}{4}T_{pwm}$ (which corresponds to the results from Fig. 34) and (b) of τ_D for $f_{cr} = 0.14f_{pwm}$ (which corresponds to the results from Fig. 35). The results are obtained from the simplified s -domain analytical model which involves representing all the delay elements as a lumped delay τ_D in the direct path.

Next, similar as in Section 5.3.6, dependence of λ_{min} on f_{cr} and τ_d is shown in Fig. 42(a) and (b), which corresponds to the results from Fig. 34 and Fig. 35, respectively. As seen, the reasoning about the impact of f_{cr} and τ_d on the all-port MIMO passivity that was made in Section 5.3.6 from the plots of P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} is in agreement with the trends of λ_{min} . Still, compared to P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} , λ_{min} seems to be less sensitive to variations of τ_d . Moreover, contrary to P_1 , P_2 , and P_{12} , λ_{min} provides limited physical insight on the converter's active behaviour, e.g., whether it is related to the input port, the output port or the coupling between them, etc. Nevertheless, the minimum eigenvalue-based approach may also be advantageous to use, as it characterizes the all-port MIMO admittance passivity by a single parameter only (also when the dimension of $\mathbf{Y}(s)$ is higher than 2 e.g., for multi-port or ac-dc converters). A more detailed discussion about the strengths and weaknesses of the minimum eigenvalue-based, i.e., the input feedforward passivity index-based, and the principal minors-based approach for describing the converter's all-port MIMO admittance passivity is out of the scope of this report and is, therefore, left for future work. Finally, in order to provide more physical insight into the design process, the use of relative passivity index [109] should be explored in future studies.

6 Multiport Y-Converter for Interlinking DC systems with the Three-Phase AC Grid

6.1 Introduction and Background

The increasing adoption of renewable energy sources (RESs), energy storage systems (ESSs), and electric vehicle charging stations necessitates traditional power systems to accommodate larger capacities and loads. In response, dc microgrids (MGs) are emerging as a viable solution for effectively integrating distributed energy sources and storage systems into existing power systems while meeting local demand [2, 110]. Several studies have investigated the optimal voltage level selection for low-voltage dc MGs [111–113]. The findings of these studies have identified 400 V dc voltage level as the preferred choice for residential and commercial applications, attributed to its superior overall system efficiency and the need for fewer power conversion stages when connecting multiple energy sources and loads. To ensure sustained and reliable operation, dc MGs are often interconnected with utility grids through a bidirectional power converter called interlinking converter (IC). This converter enables the exchange of power between the dc MGs and the utility grid, helping to maintain power balance within the dc MGs.

Both isolated and non-isolated converters have been explored in the literature for implementing the IC [114, 115]. To enhance the efficiency and power density of the IC, non-isolated converters are preferred, particularly since galvanic isolation is not mandatory according to relevant standards [116, 117].

6.1.1 Two-port Interlinking Converters

When integrating 400 V dc MG with the European low-voltage (LV) three-phase ac grid, which operates at a line-to-line voltage of $400 V_{\text{RMS}}$, buck-type three-phase converters are commonly employed to establish a single-stage power interface [118]. Several optimized buck-type converters have been proposed in the literature to serve as ICs, including current source converters (CSCs) in both six-switch and seven-switch configurations [119, 120]. The bidirectional power flow capability for the CSCs can be attained through an inverting link [121]. Additionally, other notable options include the Swiss converter [122], the integrated active filter converter [123], and the Y-converter [124, 125]. Previous studies demonstrated that the Y-converter potentially achieves superior overall performance among buck-type converters [126–128].

Besides the single-stage buck-type converter, two-stage converters can offer an alternative for interfacing 400 V dc MGs with the LV ac grid [129]. In these two-stage converters, a cascaded connection of either two-level or three-level voltage source converters (VSCs)

Figure 43: Integration of two dc MGs with the ac grid: (a) Utilizing two-port converters; (b) Utilizing a Multiport converter.

and a dc-dc step-down converter is employed. While VSCs are renowned for their simple structure, control, and high power density, the two-stage solution is less favorable, as the inclusion of an extra power conversion stage and the necessity for intermediate dc-link capacitors result in a degradation of the overall efficiency and power density of the IC [127,130].

6.1.2 Multiport Interlinking Converters: Motivations and Structures

The rising popularity of dc MGs in residential and commercial settings, as discussed in [131], has prompted a reassessment of conventional approaches to grid interfacing. Traditionally, each MG would utilize a dedicated converter for connection to the grid [114], a practice that often leads to larger system sizes and higher costs. In response to these challenges, multiport converters (MPCs) have emerged as promising and efficient solutions [5,6]. MPCs offer an effective approach by integrating multiple energy ports into a single hub, thereby providing a more streamlined and potentially cost-effective solution. Fig.43 depicts the proposed concept of using a single MPC to interface the utility grid with multiple dc MGs.

MPCs offer a multifaceted solution beyond mere cost and size reduction compared to the conventional multi-converter approach. They introduce enhanced flexibility and resilience by enabling direct power exchange between various ports. When utilized to link dc MGs with the ac grid, MPCs empower dc MGs to exchange power directly through the converter, reducing dependence on the utility grid. This strategic integration opens avenues for optimizing power flow among different energy ports and maximizing the utilization and sharing of RESs and ESSs within the dc MGs, thereby improving the overall performance

of the system.

In the literature, various MPCs have been proposed to establish a direct interface between three-phase ac grids and dc systems. These MPCs can be categorized into three groups based on the structure of the converter topology, as illustrated in Fig. 44: dc-link coupled MPCs, magnetically coupled MPCs, and modified MPC structures. dc-link coupled MPCs, depicted in Fig. 44a, are formed by interconnecting conventional two-port ac-dc and dc-dc converters to a common intermediate dc-link capacitor. This approach has been widely studied in various applications. For instance, in the field of PV generation, dc-link coupled MPCs have been explored to form a modular PV generation system based on a dc bus architecture [7]. Additionally, they have been investigated for the implementation of soft open points (SOPs) in distribution networks, where they enhance flexibility and increase the hosting capacity by integrating RESs and ESSs in multi-terminal SOPs [3,4,132]. Furthermore, dc-link coupled MPCs have been utilized for integrating RESs and ESSs into the ac grid [133].

While dc-link coupled MPCs are utilized in various applications, they suffer from significant drawbacks. As the power flow among the ports undergoes a two-stage power conversion, the efficiency of the MPC is potentially degraded. Additionally, the reliance on a common bulky intermediate dc-link capacitor [134], as depicted in Fig. 44a, increases the size of the MPC and may introduce reliability concerns [135]. Any failure or degradation of the capacitor can disrupt the operation of the entire converter. Moreover, dc-link voltage regulation may be critical, especially when power fluctuations occur at one of the ports, making prompt and robust control of the dc-link voltage is crucial [4,136].

Magnetically coupled MPCs, illustrated in Fig. 44b, incorporate magnetic coupling elements such as high-frequency (HF) transformers and coupled inductors in the converter topology for the power transfer between the ports. In [137,138], partially-isolated MPCs based on dual three-phase active bridges are introduced in three-port and four-port configurations. Another approach is demonstrated in [139,140], where an MPC combines a VSC with three-phase or single-phase converters through three HF transformers. A three-phase center-tapped HF transformer is proposed in [141] to connect two VSCs. Coupled inductors are adopted in [142] to develop a three-port inverter, while in [143], a multi-winding HF transformer is utilized to couple ac and dc ports.

The incorporation of HF transformers and coupled inductors adds to the overall complexity of the converter topology, necessitating customized and optimized designs [144]. Additionally, the presence of these magnetic components increases the volume of the MPC and introduces additional power losses, leading to reduced overall efficiency and power density of the MPC.

To address the limitations of both the dc-link coupled and magnetically coupled MPCs,

Figure 44: Different MPC structures for interfacing dc systems with the ac grid: (a) dc-coupled MPCs; (b) Magnetically-coupled MPCs; (c) Modified MPC structures.

modified MPC structures, displayed in Fig. 44c, have been developed. These modifications involve transforming two-port converters into MPCs without relying on dc-link capacitors or magnetic coupling. In [145], multilevel inverters are employed as multisource inverters, adopting classic multilevel inverter structures. However, these MPCs were originally proposed for multisource inverters, and therefore, bidirectional power flow control at all ports is not fully explored, with only limited operating modes considered [146]. Moreover, the power delivered to each port depends on the voltage ratio of the dc ports, limiting their applicability as multiport interlinking converters, especially for interfacing directly with 400 V dc systems [147]. Another MPC converter, based on the two-level VSC, is presented in [148], where each leg is simultaneously used as a buck-boost converter. However, this converter also presents constraints in the power flow and the operating range of output voltage, preventing direct connection to 400 V dc systems.

6.1.3 Motivations for the Proposed Converter

This section introduces a single-stage non-isolated MPC, named the multiport Y-converter (Y-MPC), designed to link the three-phase ac grid with 400 V dc MGs. Building upon the Y-converter, renowned for its superior performance as a buck-type IC [128], the proposed Y-MPC extends its capabilities into a multiport IC, facilitating direct power exchange between dc MGs. In applications, this enhancement aims to bolster flexibility and resilience, reduce reliance on the ac grid, and optimize the utilization and sharing of RESs and ESSs within the dc MGs. The proposed converter offers several advantages, including single-stage power conversion among different ports, potentially leading to enhanced efficiency and power density. Furthermore, the absence of bulky intermediate dc-link capacitors and HF transformers in the proposed topology favors power density and reduces costs. While designed for 400 V dc MGs in this study, the proposed MPC presents buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports, independent of the dc ports' voltage. This feature provides the flexibility to directly interface with a wide range of dc systems.

6.2 Proposed Multiport Y-converter

6.2.1 Derivation and Operation Principle

The proposed multiport converter topology is derived from the Y-converter, as depicted in Fig. 45a, transforming it from a two-port configuration into a multi-port structure capable of connecting multiple dc ports to a three-phase ac grid, as illustrated in Fig. 45b. Initially, the two-port Y-converter comprised three four-switch buck-boost modules [124, 149]. Alternatively, in the proposed converter, each module is expanded into a six-switch dc-dc converter. Considering the structure of a three-port converter, the upgraded design includes a shared buck half-bridge and two boost half-bridges, establishing connections to

Figure 45: A schematic of two-port and multiport Y-converters in a modular form: (a) Two-port Y-converter; (b) The proposed Multiport Y-converter.

the dc ports. Notably, the configuration is potentially adaptable to additional dc ports by incorporating one boost converter into each module for every extra dc port, thus maintaining scalability.

Similar to the two-port Y-converter, the three modified modules are interconnected at a central point denoted as m , serving as the neutral point for the Y-connection of the modules. Since each module functions as a dc-dc converter, maintaining a non-negative voltage on the ac side of the module ($v_{\{a,b,c\}m} \geq 0V$) is crucial. To achieve this, an offset voltage is required between the grid’s neutral point n and m . A constant offset voltage (V_{off}) is then applied, which must exceed the peak value of the ac grid phase voltage (\hat{V}_m). The ac-side voltages v_{am} , v_{bm} , and v_{cm} can be expressed as follows:

$$v_{xm}(t) = v_x(t) + V_{off} = \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x) + V_{off} \quad (32)$$

where v_x , with $x = (a, b, c)$, represents the ac grid phase voltages, ω denotes the ac grid frequency in rad/s, and θ_x signifies the respective phase angles of v_x .

Since V_{off} also represents the common-mode voltage (CMV) of the converter, the fixed CMV is an additional advantage of the proposed topology. While CMV can pose a threat to overall system performance by inducing leakage current through parasitic capacitances to ground and causing electromagnetic interference (EMI) in the high-frequency range [150], the fixed CMV in the proposed topology minimizes these issues as the leakage current flowing through parasitic capacitances is significantly reduced.

The analysis of the converter is presented by considering a single module (module a), as depicted in Fig. 46, and it similarly applies to the other modules as well. This module consists of the two inductors L_1 and L_2 along with three half-bridges: one on the ac side,

Figure 46: Module a of the proposed converter.

labeled as Bu_a , and the others on the dc sides, labeled as Bo_{a1} and Bo_{a2} . Although the main focus of this article is on interfacing 400V dc systems, the subsequent analysis is generalized for arbitrary values of V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} . Additionally, it is assumed that at least one of the dc ports' voltage is lower than the peak of the ac side voltage ($\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$), and V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} . Based on these assumptions, the Bu_a and Bo_{a1} half-bridges are under control, ensuring that only one of them is modulated at any given moment, while the other remains clamped based on the values of v_{am} and V_{dc1} , whereas Bo_{a2} will be modulated continuously.

6.2.2 Analysis and Fundamental Relations

6.2.2.1 Buck Mode When v_{am} exceeds V_{dc1} , module a operates in buck mode. In this mode, the Bu_a half-bridge switches, while the Bo_{a1} half-bridge is clamped with S_{a3} on and S_{a4} off, as illustrated in Fig. 47a. Simultaneously, the Bo_{a2} half-bridge operates with a fixed duty cycle, depending on the ratio between V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} . The duty cycles of S_{a1} and S_{a5} , denoted as d_{Bu_a} and $d_{Bo_{a2}}$, respectively, can be calculated using the following equations:

$$d_{Bu_a}(t) = \frac{V_{dc1}}{v_{am}(t)} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{off}} \quad (33)$$

$$d_{Bo_{a2}} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{V_{dc2}} \quad (34)$$

The ac grid current of phase a , denoted as i_a , is assumed to be pure sinusoidal and in

Figure 47: Operation modes of one module of the proposed converter: (a) Buck mode when $v_{am} > V_{dc1}$; (b) Boost mode when $v_{am} < V_{dc1}$

phase with its corresponding phase voltage v_a and then can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i_a(t) &= \hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t) = (\hat{I}_{m1} + \hat{I}_{m2}) \sin(\omega t) \\ &= \left(\frac{2P_{dc1}}{3\hat{V}_m} + \frac{2P_{dc2}}{3\hat{V}_m} \right) \sin(\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

where P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} represent the power delivered to dc ports 1 and 2, respectively, while \hat{I}_m denotes the peak phase current. Additionally, \hat{I}_{m1} and \hat{I}_{m2} signify the equivalent reference peak phase current solely due to the power of dc MG#1 and #2, respectively.

The summation of average inductor currents (i.e., $i_{La1,av} + i_{La2,av}$), denoted as $i_{La,av}$, can be derived by applying Kirchhoff's current law (KCL) at the ac input of the module, as follows:

$$i_{La,av}(t) = i_{La1,av}(t) + i_{La2,av}(t) = \frac{i_a(t) - i_{Cf,a}(t)}{d_{Bu_a}(t)} \quad (36)$$

where $i_{Cf,a}$ represents the current through the input capacitor C_f . By neglecting $i_{Cf,a}$, the equation can be simplified as follows:

$$i_{La,av}(t) = \frac{i_a(t)}{d_{Bu_a}(t)} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)}{d_{Bu_a}(t)} \quad (37)$$

Using (35) and (37), $i_{La1,av}$ and $i_{La2,av}$ can be determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{La1,av}(t) &= \frac{\hat{I}_{m1} \sin(\omega t)}{d_{Bu_a}} \\ i_{La2,av}(t) &= \frac{\hat{I}_{m2} \sin(\omega t)}{d_{Bu_a}} \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

6.2.2.2 Boost Mode The second mode of operation occurs when v_{am} falls below V_{dc1} . In this mode, module a operates in boost mode. In this mode, the Bo_{a1} half-bridge switches, while the Bu_a half-bridge is clamped with S_{a1} on and S_{a2} off, as depicted in Fig. 47b. Simultaneously, the Bo_{a2} half-bridge operates with a time-varying duty cycle. The duty cycles of S_{a3} , denoted as $d_{Bo_{a1}}$, and $d_{Bo_{a2}}$ can be calculated using the following equations:

$$d_{Bo_{a1}}(t) = \frac{v_{am}(t)}{V_{dc1}} \quad (39)$$

$$d_{Bo_{a2}}(t) = \frac{v_{am}(t)}{V_{dc2}} \quad (40)$$

Using (38) and given that $d_{Bu_a} = 1$ in this mode, $i_{La1,av}$ and $i_{La2,av}$ can be determined as:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{La1,av}(t) &= \hat{I}_{m1} \sin(\omega t) \\ i_{La2,av}(t) &= \hat{I}_{m2} \sin(\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Table 6: Summary of the basic equations of the proposed converter.

Parameter	Equation	Parameter	Equation
v_x	$\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)$	v_{xm}	$v_x + V_{off}$
d_{Bu_x}	$\frac{\min(v_{xm}, V_{dc1}, V_{dc2})}{V_{dc1}}$	$d_{Bo_{x1}}$	$\frac{\min(v_{xm}, V_{dc1}, V_{dc2})}{V_{dc1}}$
$d_{Bo_{x2}}$	$\frac{v_{xm}}{\min(v_{xm}, V_{dc1}, V_{dc2})}$	$i_{Lx,av}$	$\frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)}{3}$
$i_{Lx1,av}$	$\frac{2P_{dc1} \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)}{3\hat{V}_m d_{Bu_x}}$	$i_{Lx2,av}$	$\frac{2P_{dc2} \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)}{3\hat{V}_m d_{Bu_x}}$

Table 7: Parameters of the proposed converter

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated ac power	$P_{ac,r}$	10 kW
Rated dc power	$P_{dc1,r}, P_{dc2,r}$	5 kW
ac line voltage, frequency	V_{ll}, f_o	400 V, 50 Hz
dc voltage	V_{dc1}, V_{dc2}	350 V to 800 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz
Inductance	L_1, L_2	330 μ H

The key waveforms for module a of the proposed converter are plotted in Fig. 48. Additionally, the basic characteristic equations of the proposed converter are summarized in Table 6. These equations are applicable to any values of V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} , including the scenario presented in the analysis (where V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2}) and also when V_{dc1} is higher than V_{dc2} .

6.3 Topology Evaluation for Wide-range of dc Ports Voltage

The voltage and current stresses of the semiconductor devices of the proposed converter are analyzed in this section. This analysis aids in appropriately sizing and selecting the semiconductor devices. The converter's specifications and ratings are outlined in Table 7, assuming the converter's connection to the European low-voltage grid via its ac port and interfacing with two dc ports ranging from 350 V to 800 V. The ac and dc power ratings are selected for residential and commercial applications and are chosen to be 10 kW and 5 kW, respectively.

In addition to the stresses on semiconductor devices, the conduction and switching losses of the devices are presented at rated power for different voltage levels of the dc ports.

6.3.1 Semiconductor devices stresses

6.3.1.1 Voltage stresses The ac-side buck half-bridges process the ac-side voltages $v_{(a,b,c)m}$, respectively. Therefore, the related switches are subjected to a time-varying volt-

Figure 48: Key waveforms of module a of the proposed converter.

age of maximum value that equals $\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$. Meanwhile, the dc-side boost half-bridges present voltage stress equal to their respective dc port voltage.

6.3.1.2 Current stresses The RMS current stresses of the semiconductor devices at rated power are displayed in Fig. 49 using fitted contour plots. As stated in the previous section, the presented analysis assumes that at least one of the dc ports' voltage is lower than $\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$. In the presented current stresses plot, one of the dc ports is always limited to 600 V, while the other can reach the specified rated dc voltage (i.e., 800 V).

Considering the current stresses of the $Bu, (a, b, c)$ switches ($S_{(a,b,c)1}, S_{(a,b,c)2}$), the current stresses increase as the dc ports' voltage decreases due to higher values of i_{La1} and i_{La2} in buck mode. Conversely, as the dc ports' voltage increases, the current stresses decrease, especially for $S_{(a,b,c)2}$, where the current stresses at the high voltage limits of the dc ports are four times lower than the current stresses at the low voltage limits.

For the current stresses of the $Bo(a, b, c)1$ and $Bo(a, b, c)2$ switches, as in a typical dc-dc boost converter, the current stresses of the upper switches ($S_{(a,b,c)3}, S_{(a,b,c)5}$) increase as their corresponding dc port voltage decreases, while the current stresses of the lower switches ($S_{(a,b,c)4}, S_{(a,b,c)6}$) increase as their corresponding dc port voltage increases.

6.3.2 Semiconductor devices losses

The semiconductor losses of the proposed converter are evaluated through simulations, considering 1.2 kV SiC MOSFETs. For $S_{(a,b,c)1}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)2}$, a SiC MOSFET with nominal on-state resistance of 30 m Ω (IMZ120R030M1H) is selected, while for the other devices, a 60 m Ω SiC MOSFET (IMZ120R060M1H) is chosen.

The fitted contour plots of conduction losses, switching losses, and total semiconductor losses are presented in Fig. 50. Conduction losses are maximum at low dc port voltages, primarily due to their significant dependence on the higher current stress of devices $S_{(a,b,c)1}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)2}$. Consequently, the trend of the conduction losses contour plot closely mirrors the contour plot of the current stresses of $S_{(a,b,c)1}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)2}$.

The switching losses of the proposed converter are primarily influenced by two factors: the inductor current, equivalent to the switching current of the devices, which increases at low dc port voltages, and the dc ports' voltage, equivalent to the switching voltage of $Boost, (a, b, c)1$ and $Boost, (a, b, c)2$ devices. As a result, switching losses are maximum when one of the dc ports' voltage is minimized while the other is maximized.

Finally, the calculated total semiconductor losses for the selected devices range from 100 W to 180 W, constituting 1% to 1.8% of the converter's rated power.

Figure 49: Fitted contour plots illustrating the RMS current stresses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.

Figure 50: Fitted contour plots illustrating the power losses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.

Table 8: Parameters of the proposed converter.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated ac power	$P_{ac,r}$	10 kW
Rated dc power	$P_{dc1,r}, P_{dc2,r}$	5 kW
ac line voltage, frequency	V_{ll}, f_o	400 V, 50 Hz
dc MG voltage	V_{dc1}, V_{dc2}	400 V ($\pm 10\%$)
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz
Inductance	L_1, L_2	330 μ H

6.4 Topology Comparison and Evaluation

6.4.1 Evaluation of the Proposed converter against two Y-converters

This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of semiconductor losses of the proposed converter compared to the use of two separate Y-converters for integrating the two dc MGs with the ac grid. The objective of this evaluation is to demonstrate the advantages of adopting the proposed Y-MPC in enhancing the efficiency of the power electronic interface between the ac grid and the dc MGs. The specifications and ratings guiding the evaluation are summarized in Table 8. The chosen power level for the power exchange of each MG is 5 kW, which is selected for small-scale residential and commercial MGs. Therefore, two Y-converters rated at 5 kW each are adopted, while the Y-MPC is rated at 10 kW. The losses of the inductors L_1 and L_2 are not included in the comparison as both solutions exhibit the same inductor current waveforms, and the same values of inductors are adopted in both solutions.

For both the proposed converter and Y-converter, the ac-side half-bridges commute at v_{xm} , which reaches a peak value of $\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$. Since V_{off} must surpass \hat{V}_m , the peak value is 665 V when V_{off} equals 340 V. Consequently, 1200 V SiC MOSFETs are chosen for the ac-side half-bridges in both converters. On the other hand, the dc-side half-bridges operate at the dc MG voltage (400 V), allowing the use of 650 V SiC MOSFETs for the dc-side devices in both converters.

In this assessment, SiC MOSFETs from Infineon are utilized. For the dc-side half-bridges, 650 V SiC MOSFETs with a nominal on-state resistance R_{ds} of 57 m Ω (IMZA65R057M1H) are selected for both converters. For the ac-side half-bridges, 1200 V SiC MOSFETs with R_{ds} of 40 m Ω and 20 m Ω (IMZA120R040M1H, IMZA120R020M1H) are chosen for the Y-converter and the Y-MPC respectively. This selection is based on the higher current stresses endured by the ac-side half-bridges in the Y-MPC, handling double the rated power compared to those in the Y-converter. Additionally, the junction temperature T_j of each device is calculated using PLECS thermal modeling simulations to ensure that the T_j of every device remains below 120 °C for all possible operating conditions.

The semiconductor losses of both converters are evaluated using PLECS while P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} are swept from -5 kW to 5 kW, covering all possible operating conditions for the proposed case study. The calculated semiconductor losses of both converters are reported in Fig. 51. At the rated power in rectification mode (i.e., when P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW), the Y-MPC exhibits semiconductor losses equal to 113.9 W, while the two Y-converters exhibit total semiconductor losses equal to 110.5 W. At the rated power in inversion mode (i.e., when P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to -5 kW), the Y-MPC exhibits semiconductor losses equal to 119.7 W, while the two Y-converters exhibit total semiconductor losses equal to 117.2 W. Accordingly, both solutions attain almost the same semiconductor losses at rated power in both rectification and inversion modes, with slightly higher losses for the Y-MPC, mainly driven by the increased current stress on the ac-side half-bridges.

Although both converters exhibit similar semiconductor losses at rated power in both rectification and inversion modes, the proposed Y-MPC features significantly reduced losses for most of the operating range, especially at light-load and when the two dc MGs are directly transferring power between themselves. When a dc MG needs to absorb active power while the other MG has an excess of power generation, the Y-MPC enables direct power sharing between the dc MGs, with the ac grid is only responsible for compensating the resultant power difference.

For instance, when P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal 5 kW and -5 kW respectively, the Y-MPC allows for direct power transfer from dc MG#1 to dc MG#2 through the dc-side half-bridges, while the ac-side half-bridges do not exchange the power with the ac grid. On the other hand, in the two Y-converters, both ac-side and dc-side half-bridges handle the power, resulting in increased semiconductor losses compared to the Y-MPC. At P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW and -5 kW, the Y-MPC exhibits semiconductor losses equal to 66.5 W, while the two Y-converters exhibit total semiconductor losses equal to 115.3 W, showcasing the significant reduction in semiconductor losses gained by the proposed Y-MPC.

The semiconductor losses breakdown for the two Y-converters and the Y-MPC is displayed in Fig. 51b and Fig. 51d, respectively, with P_{dc1} set to 5 kW and P_{dc2} swept from -5 kW to 5 kW. The losses are categorized into conduction losses of ac-side devices $P_{cond(ac)}$, conduction losses of dc-side devices $P_{cond(dc)}$, switching losses of ac-side devices $P_{sw(ac)}$, and switching losses of dc-side devices $P_{sw(dc)}$. The breakdown highlights that the reduction in losses is attributed to the decrease in conduction and switching losses of the ac-side devices, achieved by enabling direct power sharing between dc MG#1 and dc MG#2 through the proposed Y-MPC.

The presented evaluations show that the proposed Y-MPC offers superior performance compared to the two Y-converters. This enhanced performance includes a reduction in semiconductor device count from 24 to 18 devices, along with their corresponding driving

Figure 51: Evaluation of the semiconductor losses using PLECS: (a) For two Y-converters at different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} ; (b) Semiconductor losses breakdown of two Y-converters at P_{dc1} equal to 5 kW and different values of P_{dc2} ; (c) For the proposed converter at different values of P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} ; (d) Semiconductor losses breakdown of the proposed converter at P_{dc1} equal to 5 kW and different values of P_{dc2}

Table 9: Specifications utilized in converters evaluation

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated ac power	$P_{ac,r}$	± 10 kW
Rated dc power	$P_{dc1,r}, P_{dc2,r}$	± 5 kW
ac line voltage, frequency	V_{ll}, f_o	400 V, 50 Hz
dc voltage	V_{dc1}, V_{dc2}	400 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz

circuitry. Additionally, it facilitates direct power sharing between the dc MGs, which is beneficial for minimizing dependence on the ac grid and improving the utilization of energy sources and storage in the dc MGs. Furthermore, this direct power sharing contributes to the improved efficiency of the power electronic interface, as demonstrated in Fig. 51a and Fig. 51c, where the larger blue area in the Y-MPC semiconductor losses plot indicates reduced losses compared to the two Y-converters across most of the operating range.

6.4.2 Evaluation of the Proposed converter against the dc-link coupled MPC using VSC and IBs

VSC is typically chosen as the interface converter between the three-phase ac grid and the dc systems due to its simple structure, control, and high power density. However, when interfacing the 400 V dc MGs with the European LV ac grid (operating with a line-to-line voltage of $400 V_{RMS}$), an additional step-down stage is required. This step-down stage is implemented using three-phase IBs to minimize current stresses on the semiconductor devices and reduce the size of the buck stage inductors.

Fig. 52a illustrates, in a modular representation, the cascaded connection between the VSC and the three-phase IBs to form MPC. The VSC and IBs are connected to the same dc-link, which is controlled at a fixed voltage of 700 V, given that the VSC operates with sinusoidal pulse width modulation. Key waveforms are depicted in Fig. 52b, including voltage, ac grid current, and inductor current waveforms.

In this section, the power converters are evaluated in terms of stresses, losses, the total chip area of semiconductor devices, and the total size of magnetic elements. For semiconductor devices, the selection criteria are discussed along with the estimation of the corresponding total chip area. The semiconductor is also evaluated using PLECS simulation for the entire power range.

For magnetic elements, a simplified analytical method is presented for magnetic element design and volume estimation to meet the CISPR 11 Class B EMI standard for the ac grid. The specifications and ratings utilized in the evaluation are summarized in Table 9. The ac and dc power ratings are selected for residential and commercial applications and are chosen to be ± 10 kW and ± 5 kW, respectively.

(a) Schematic of the VSC+IBs

(b) Key waveforms of the VSC+IBs

Figure 52: Schematic and key waveforms of the VSC+IBs.

Table 10: Selected SiC devices for converters evaluation

Device symbol	VSC+IBs	Y-MPC
$S_{(a,b,c)1}$	IMZA120R040M1H	IMZ120R030M1H
$S_{(a,b,c)2}$	IMZA120R040M1H	IMZ120R060M1H
$S_{(a,b,c)3,5}$	IMZ120R140M1H	IMZA65R057M1H
$S_{(a,b,c)4,6}$	IMZ120R140M1H	IMZA65R107M1H

6.4.2.1 Evaluation of Semiconductor Devices The initial step in device selection involves determining their voltage ratings based on the specific stresses encountered in the converter configurations. For the VSC+IBs, where all devices experience a voltage stress equal to the dc-link voltage V_{link} (700 V), 1200 V SiC devices are chosen. In the case of the Y-MPC, the ac-side buck half-bridges handle voltages with a peak value of $\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$ (655 V at V_{off} equals 340 V), justifying the use of 1200 V SiC devices. Meanwhile, the dc-side boost half-bridges are subjected to the respective dc port voltage (400 V), allowing the adoption of 650 V SiC devices.

The CoolSiC discrete MOSFETs from Infineon are chosen for the evaluation, with the desired voltage ratings of 1200 V (IMZ120, IMZA120) and 650 V (IMZA65). To assess the chip area of the devices, it is assumed that the specific on-resistance $R_{ds,sp}$ remains constant for all devices with the same voltage rating. Specifically, it is set at $200 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ mm}^{-2}$ and $350 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ mm}^{-2}$ for the 650 V and 1200 V devices, respectively [151, 152].

The selection criterion for the SiC devices is to achieve the lowest overall semiconductor chip area for the converter. Starting from the devices with the highest R_{ds} , the junction temperature of each device is calculated using PLECS thermal modeling. The device is selected if its junction temperature is below 125°C ; otherwise, the device with a lower R_{ds} is chosen until the temperature criterion is met. In addition to the PLECS Foster model for the thermal chain between the device chip and case, a thermal resistance is added to the model to represent the case to heat sink resistance and it is assumed to be equal for all devices and equal to 0.3 KW^{-1} . Accordingly, the selected devices for each converter are presented in Table 10.

Fig. 53 summarizes the evaluation of semiconductor devices for the two converters. It presents the voltage and current stresses, along with the total chip area for each converter. The Y-MPC exhibits a slightly higher total chip area than the VSC+IBs, with only a 2.8% increment. Considering that the theoretical limit for $R_{ds,sp}$ of 1200 V SiC devices is four times the limit for $R_{ds,sp}$ of 650 V SiC devices, advancements in SiC devices manufacturing towards the nearly ideal theoretical limits could potentially alter the evaluation results in favor of the Y-MPC.

The semiconductor losses of the converters across the entire power range, evaluated using PLECS simulation, are illustrated in Fig. 54. The Y-MPC exhibits higher conduction

Figure 53: Evaluation of both converters in terms of semiconductor stresses and chip area.

losses due to relatively higher current stresses compared to VSC+IBs. However, the Y-MPC achieves significantly lower switching losses since not all devices are continuously commutating. This is in contrast to VSC+IBs, where all devices continuously commute, subjecting them to the V_{link} voltage stress. Overall, semiconductor losses demonstrate that the Y-MPC outperforms VSC+IBs across the entire power range. At rated power in rectification mode, semiconductor losses for Y-MPC and VSC+IBs are 149 W and 172 W, respectively. For rated power in inversion mode, the losses are 164 W for Y-MPC and 173 W for VSC+IBs.

6.4.2.2 Evaluation of Magnetic Elements The VSC+IBs configuration includes three distinct magnetic elements: the VSC inductance L_{ac} , the IBs inductors $L_{dc(1,2)}$, and the EMI filter inductor L_f . The selection of L_{ac} directly influences the total harmonic distortion (THD) and the resultant high-frequency noise generated by its switching ripple current. Studies recommend allowing for a maximum peak-to-peak ripple current $\Delta I_{L_{ac},pkpk}$ ranging from 20% to 40% of the peak grid current to limit the peak switching current and high-frequency losses [153]. In this evaluation, $\Delta I_{L_{ac},pkpk}$ is set to be 40%, aiming to reduce the inductor's volume. Similarly, for $L_{dc(1,2)}$, the peak-to-peak ripple current $\Delta I_{L_{dc},pkpk}$ is set to be 60% for each inductor. The design equations for L_{ac} and $L_{dc(1,2)}$ are as follows:

$$L_{ac} = \frac{1}{\Delta I_{L_{ac},pkpk} f_{sw}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2} V_{ll} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{6}\right)}{\left(\frac{2}{3} V_{link} - \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} V_{ll}\right) V_{link}} \quad (42)$$

$$L_{dc(1,2)} = \frac{1}{\Delta I_{L_{dc(1,2)},pk-pk} f_{sw}} \cdot \frac{V_{dc(1,2)}(V_{link} - V_{dc(1,2)})}{V_{link}} \quad (43)$$

Figure 54: Fitted contour plots illustrating the power losses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.

In the Y-MPC, the generated high-frequency noise is dependent on the operating mode. In buck mode, the converter exhibits a switched high-frequency current, while in boost mode, it exhibits a triangular high-frequency current. The peak RMS value of the high-frequency ripple current in both modes can be calculated as follows [154]:

$$I_{hf_{RMS}} = \begin{cases} \hat{I}_m \sqrt{\frac{\hat{V}_m + V_{off}}{V_{dc(1,2)}} - 1} & \text{Buck mode} \\ \frac{V_{dc(1,2)}}{8\sqrt{3} L_{1,2} f_{sw}} & \text{Boost mode} \end{cases} \quad (44)$$

where \hat{I}_m is the peak grid current.

A minimum limit for L_1 and L_2 can be defined to restrict $I_{hf_{RMS}}$ in both buck and boost modes to the same value. For the presented case study, the minimum limit for L_1 and L_2 is set at 50 μH . To limit the peak switching current and core losses, L_1 and L_2 are chosen to be 150 μH .

For the EMI filter design, high-frequency emissions are calculated, and accordingly, the required attenuation to meet CISPR 11 Class B is defined, and the passive components are designed. The $I_{hf_{RMS}}$ at the first switching harmonic that falls into the EMI standard limit (above 150 kHz), denoted as $I_{hf-h_{RMS}}$, can be calculated as follows:

$$I_{hf-h_{RMS}} = \begin{cases} \frac{V_{link}}{8\sqrt{3} L_{ac} f_{sw} n_h^2} & \text{VSC+IBs} \\ \frac{\hat{I}_m}{n_h} \sqrt{\frac{\hat{V}_m + V_{off}}{V_{dc(1,2)}} - 1} & \text{Y-MPC} \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

where n_h is the switching harmonic order (equals to 3 at the selected f_{sw}).

The required attenuation by the EMI filter in dB μV , denoted as ATT , can be determined for both converters as follows:

$$ATT = V_{hf-h_{RMS}} - V_{CISPR} + 10 \quad (46)$$

where $V_{hf-h_{RMS}}$ is the noise in dB μV generated from $I_{hf-h_{RMS}}$ considering a 50 Ω LISN, and V_{CISPR} is the specified noise limit at the switching harmonic in dB μV with an additional margin of 10 dB μV . For a multi-stage LC filter with n_f input filter stages equal to 3, the product of filter inductance L_f and capacitance C_f is calculated as:

$$L_f C_f = \frac{10^{ATT/(20n_f)}}{(2\pi n_h f_{sw})^2} \quad (47)$$

Finally, L_f can be calculated by selecting the total filter capacitance to limit its reactive

Figure 55: Evaluation of converters in terms of inductors volume.

power to 5% of $P_{ac,r}$ and then using (47) to calculate L_f .

A simple approach to estimate the inductor volume is presented in [130]. The estimated total inductors volume of both converters is illustrated in Fig. 55 where the Y-MPC yields a total inductors volume equal to 81% of the VSC+IBs inductors volume.

6.5 Control and Modulation

The operation of the converter is determined based on two power references P_{dc1}^* and P_{dc2}^* assumed to be assigned to the dc ports. In practical applications, such power references may be adjusted by a dc microgrid controller to achieve desired power balances among the ports or they may vary based on the measured voltage level at the dc ports, in a droop-like control fashion.

Fig. 56a displays the overall control organization. The implementation of the several control sub-blocks is provided and discussed in the following by referring to Fig. 56b-Fig. 56f. Considering Fig. 56a, the two power references P_{dc1}^* and P_{dc2}^* are first translated into a power reference P_{ac}^* for the ac port of the converter, which is actually controlled as a current source to ensure a regulated power transfer with desired power factor at the ac port and the exchange of pure sinusoidal currents with the grid connected at the port. A second current controller is employed to regulate the current exchanged at the dc port with higher dc voltage.

By utilizing (35), P_{ac}^* is translated into the reference peak phase current, denoted as \hat{I}_m^* , which is subsequently input to the synchronization stage. The synchronization stage

Figure 56: A detailed block diagram illustrating the control structure of the proposed converter: (a) The overall block diagram of the proposed control structure; (b) A detailed description of current controller 1 block; (c) A detailed description of current controller 2 block; (d) A detailed description of Bu_x modulators; (e) A detailed description of Bo_{x1} modulators; and (f) A detailed description of Bo_{x2} modulators.

Table 11: Parameters of the PI controllers adopted in the current control loops.

Parameter	Symbol	Equation
Cross-over frequency	f_c	$\frac{f_{sw}}{15}$
Proportional gain	K_p	$2\pi f_c L$
Integral gain	K_i	$K_p f_c$

is responsible for generating sinusoidal grid current references, denoted as i_x^* , for the grid current control loop, displayed in Fig. 56b. The ac grid currents are estimated based on measurements of the inductors' currents: by utilizing (53), i_x can be calculated by multiplying $i_{Lx,av}$ by d_{bu_x} . This approach allows the regulation of both the grid and the inductor currents without the need of additional cascaded loops. Subsequently, the reference and feedback currents in the abc frame are controlled by linear regulators in the $\alpha\beta$ frame. The output of the ac grid current controller is directed to the Bu_x modulator and the Bo_{x1} or the Bo_{x1} modulators based on the state of Logic 1 and Logic 2, as indicated in Fig. 56a. The logic allows to connect the ac current controller output to the modulator of the dc port with lower voltage. For Logic 1, its input 1 is selected when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} , input 2 is selected otherwise. Logic 2 operates complementarily, connecting input 2 to its output when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} or input 1 otherwise.

The second current controller in Fig. 56a is employed to regulate the power of the dc port with higher voltage. The reference of this controller is determined based on the power reference provided by Logic 2 (i.e., P_{dc2}^* when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} , P_{dc1}^* otherwise). Subsequently, the power reference is translated into the equivalent reference peak phase current attributable to the port with higher voltage (i.e., \hat{I}_{m2}^* when V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} , it is \hat{I}_{m1}^* otherwise). The reference peak current is fed into the synchronization stage to generate the sinusoidal current references for the current controller. The controller, detailed in Fig. 56c, employs the reference inductors currents of the dc port with higher voltage, defined using (38) and regulates the inductors currents in the abc frame, to prevent circulating currents in the converter. Similar to the ac grid current controllers, the output of the controllers is directed to either Bo_{x1} or Bo_{x1} modulators based on Logic 1 and Logic 2.

In the experimental verification, PI controllers were adopted in the current control loops. The specifications of the PI controllers are summarized in Table 11, assuming that $L_1 = L_2 = L$.

Finally, Fig. 56d, Fig. 56e, and Fig. 56f display the modulators for Bu_x , Bo_{x1} , and Bo_{x2} , respectively. These modulators are based on the equations for Bu_x , Bo_{x1} , and Bo_{x1} summarized in Table 6. For all modulators, the instantaneous minimum value of v_{am} , V_{dc1} , and V_{dc2} is defined. After adding the controllers' action, this value is divided by the corresponding dc-link voltage of the modulator's half-bridges to determine the duty cycle.

6.6 Simulation results

Simulation results of the proposed converter are presented in this section to showcase its performance under different operating conditions. The simulations consider rated ac grid voltage and V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively. Additionally, the power delivered to V_{dc1} (P_{dc1}) is fixed at 5 kW.

Three different operating conditions are presented. In the first operating condition, demonstrated in Fig. 57, P_{dc2} is set to 5 kW, indicating that both dc systems are absorbing power from the ac grid. As evident from the waveforms, these simulation results match the waveforms discussed in the analysis section, exhibiting pure sinusoidal ac grid currents and positive ac module voltages, given that V_{off} is selected to equal 340 V.

In Fig. 58, P_{dc2} is set to 0 kW. In this case, power flows only from the ac grid to V_{dc1} , and the average current flowing in the L_2 inductors is controlled to zero, with only a high-frequency ripple current flowing through L_2 .

The third operating condition is displayed in Fig. 59 where P_{dc2} is set to -5 kW. In this case, both dc systems are directly exchanging active power through the proposed converter, and hence no active power is drawn from the ac grid. The ac grid currents are minimized, and only the current due to the reactive power drawn by C_f flows.

6.7 Experimental results

In this section, preliminary results collected from the experimental prototype are reported. A detailed discussion of the experimental prototype and various results under different operating conditions are planned to be included in the second deliverable of WP3 (D3.2). Fig. 60 depicts the experimental setup of the proposed converter, which serves the purpose of validating its operation and confirming the accuracy of the presented waveforms. The prototype consists of six Imperix SIC power modules (PEB8024 with C2M0080120D SiC MOSFETs) for the boost half-bridges and three half-bridges with UF4SC120023K4S SiC MOSFETs featuring lower on-state resistance compared to the boost half-bridges devices due to higher current stresses. Control is achieved using two B-box controllers configured in a master-slave arrangement. The emulation of AC grid and DC systems is facilitated by bidirectional AC and DC power supplies. A single-stage input filter, with parameters $L_f = 1.2$ mH and $C_f = 10$ μ F, is utilized, while 330 μ H inductors are employed for L_1 and L_2 .

The experimental waveforms in Fig. 61 depict the operation of the converter with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 360 V and 400 V, respectively, while the ac grid voltage remains at its rated value. Both P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} are set to 3 kW, indicating that both MGs are absorbing power from the AC grid. As evident from the waveforms, the AC currents demonstrate sinusoidal behavior and are well-synchronized with the AC voltages, resulting in a measured power factor of 0.99. The measured efficiency of the prototype at this operating point is 94.75%.

Figure 57: Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} equal to 5 kW and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW.

Figure 58: Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} equal to 0 kW and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW.

Figure 59: Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} equal to -5 kW and P_{dc2} equal to 5 kW.

Figure 60: Picture of the experimental prototype of the proposed converter.

Figure 61: Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} are set to 360 V and 400 V and with P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} both equal to 3 kW.

7 Asymmetric Multiport Y-Converter for Interlinking DC systems with the Three-Phase AC Grid

7.1 Introduction and Background

Interlinking converters (ICs), connecting 400 V dc MGs with the utility grid, can be categorized based on power levels into single-phase and three-phase ICs. When the IC's power level is limited to a few kilowatts, single-phase ICs are commonly employed. For these single-phase ICs, the two-stage approach is typically adopted to minimize the dc-link capacitance [155]. The first stage involves a single-phase bidirectional converter, while the second stage can incorporate either isolated or non-isolated dc-dc converters. Numerous studies have investigated single-phase ICs, evaluating various combinations of the first and second stage converters in terms of total efficiency, power density, and cost [156].

When targeting higher power levels for the IC, three-phase ICs are utilized. Several single-stage buck-type converters, including the current source converter, the Swiss converter, and the Y-converter, have undergone evaluation [122, 125]. Among these converters, the Y-converter has demonstrated superior overall performance in terms of both efficiency and power density [128]. Additionally, literature discusses two-stage converters formed by connecting a voltage source converter (VSC) in cascade with an additional step-down stage. However, the two-stage solution is less favorable, as the inclusion of an extra power conversion stage and the necessity for intermediate dc link capacitors result in a degradation of the overall efficiency and power density of the IC.

The growing prevalence of dc MGs in residential and commercial applications has prompted a reevaluation of the conventional approach, where a dedicated converter is assigned to each MG for grid interfacing. This traditional method can result in increased system size and costs. Moreover, the use of single-phase ICs may contribute to voltage imbalances in the utility grid due to unequalized loading across the three phases. An efficient and promising alternative to address these challenges is the adoption of multiport converters (MPCs) [5, 6]. MPCs consolidate multiple energy ports into a single hub, offering a more streamlined and cost-effective solution. Fig. 62 depicts the concept of using a single MPC to interface the utility grid with multiple dc MGs.

MPCs not only provide a means to reduce overall size and costs compared to the multi-converter approach but also bring about flexibility and resilience by facilitating direct power flow between different ports. When linking dc MGs with the ac grid, MPCs empower dc MGs to exchange power directly through the converter, reducing reliance on the utility grid. This strategy creates possibilities for optimizing power flow among various energy ports and optimizing the utilization of energy sources and storages in MGs, thereby improving

Figure 62: Interfacing two dc microgrids with the ac grid: (a) Employing two converters - a single-phase and a three-phase bidirectional converter based on the dc microgrid power level; and (b) Employing a multiport converter.

the overall efficiency and reliability of the system.

In this section, a non-isolated MPC is proposed to interface the three-phase ac grid with the 400 V dc MGs. The proposed MPC aims to provide a more compact and efficient power interface by reducing the number of semiconductor devices, passive elements, and EMI filters compared to the multi-converter approach, as presented in Fig. 43, while maintaining balanced ac grid currents. The proposed converter features an asymmetric structure, enabling the integration of the lower power dc systems into the three-phase IC with a minimum number of components. The motivations for the proposed converter include its single-stage power conversion among different ports, allowing for potentially enhanced efficiency and power density. Additionally, although designed for the 400 V dc MGs in this study, the proposed MPC features a buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports, providing the flexibility to directly interface with a wide range of dc systems.

7.2 Principle of Operation and Analysis

The proposed converter builds upon the Y-converter, as introduced in [124], transforming it from a two-port configuration into a multi-port one capable of connecting multiple dc systems to a three-phase ac grid. In its original form, the two-port Y-converter comprised three four-switch buck-boost modules, as demonstrated in Fig. 63a. To develop the multiport converter, the four-switch buck-boost converter is expanded into a six-switch buck-boost converter formed with a shared buck half-bridge and two boost half-bridges. This can be developed in a symmetric or asymmetric configuration. In the symmetric configuration presented in Fig. 63b, the extension from a four-switch to a six-switch buck-boost converter is applied to the three modules. While in the asymmetric configuration presented

Figure 63: Different configurations of the modular Y-converter: (a) The two-port Y-converter, (b) The symmetric multiport Y-converter (Y-MPC), and (c) The asymmetric multiport Y-converter (AY-MPC).

in Fig. 63c, the extension from a four-switch to a six-switch buck-boost converter is applied only to one of the modules.

The asymmetric multiport Y-converter, denoted as AY-MPC, offers a reduced structure with a lower number of semiconductor devices and inductors compared to the symmetric multiport Y-converter, denoted as Y-MPC. For the presented case study where the two dc systems have different power levels, the AY-MPC enables the integration of the lower power dc system into the three-phase IC with a minimum number of components, allowing for a simpler structure and a compact size. However, a challenge in the AY-MPC is to maintain balanced ac-grid currents, a topic that will be addressed in this section.

In the AY-MPC, similar to the two-port Y-converter, the three modules are interconnected at a central point denoted as m , which functions as the neutral point for the Y-connection of the modules. As each module serves as a dc-dc converter, it is crucial to maintain a non-

Figure 64: Module a of the proposed converter.

negative voltage on the ac side of the module ($v_{\{a,b,c\}m} \geq 0V$). To achieve this, an offset voltage is necessary between grid neutral point n and m . A constant offset voltage (V_{off}) is then applied, which should be higher than the peak value of the ac grid phase voltage (\hat{V}_m). The ac-side voltages v_{am} , v_{bm} , and v_{cm} can be mathematically expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 v_{am} &= \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{off} \\
 v_{bm} &= \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t - 2\pi/3) + V_{off} \\
 v_{cm} &= \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + 2\pi/3) + V_{off}
 \end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

where ω is the ac grid frequency in rad/s.

The analysis of the converter is presented by considering module a depicted in Fig. 64, while the other modules will remain in the same operation as the two-port Y-converter [124]. Additionally, in the subsequent analysis, it is assumed that at least one of the dc ports' voltage is lower than the peak of the ac side voltage ($\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$), and V_{dc1} is lower than V_{dc2} . Other operation modes, such as when V_{dc2} is lower than V_{dc1} , are not discussed in the article. Module a consists of the two inductors L_1 and L_2 along with three half-bridges: one on the ac side, labeled as *Buck a*, and the others on the dc sides, labeled as *Boost a1* and *Boost a2*. Based on these assumptions, the *Buck a* and *Boost a1* half-bridges are under control, ensuring that only one of them is modulated at any given moment, while the other remains clamped based on the values of v_{am} and V_{dc1} , whereas *Boost a2* will be modulated continuously.

When v_{am} is greater than V_{dc1} , that is, when $t_1 < t < t_2$, as illustrated in Fig. 65, the *Buck a* half-bridge keeps switching, while the *Boost a1* half-bridge is clamped with S_{a3} on and S_{a4} off. To determine the duty cycle of S_{a1} , denoted as $d_{buck,a}$, the following calculation can be

applied:

$$d_{buck,a} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{v_{am}} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{off}} \quad (49)$$

For the *Boost a2* half-bridge, it operates with a fixed duty cycle during this period, depending on the ratio between V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} . The duty cycle of S_{a5} , denoted as $d_{boost,a2}$, can be calculated as follows:

$$d_{boost,a2} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{V_{dc2}} \quad (50)$$

The ac grid current of phase a , denoted as i_a , is assumed to be pure sinusoidal and in phase with its corresponding phase voltage v_a and then can be calculated as follows:

$$i_a = \hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t) = \frac{2(P_{dc1} + P_{dc2})}{3\hat{V}_m} \sin(\omega t) \quad (51)$$

where P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} represent the power delivered to dc ports 1 and 2, respectively, and \hat{I}_m denotes the peak phase current.

The summation of average inductor currents (i.e., $i_{La1,av} + i_{La2,av}$), denoted as $i_{La,av}$, can be derived by applying Kirchhoff's Current Law (KCL) at the ac input of the module, as follows:

$$i_{La,av} = i_{La1,av} + i_{La2,av} = \frac{i_a - i_{Cf,a}}{d_{buck,a}} \quad (52)$$

where $i_{Cf,a}$ represents the current through the input capacitor C_f . By neglecting $i_{Cf,a}$, the equation can be simplified as follows:

$$i_{La,av} = \frac{i_a}{d_{buck,a}} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)}{d_{buck,a}} \quad (53)$$

In order to maintain a balanced ac-grid currents, i_{La2} is controlled to deliver the required P_{dc2} to dc port 2 while i_{La1} is controlled to ensure balanced current at the ac grid. Using (53), $i_{La2,av}$ and $i_{La1,av}$ can be determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{La2,av} &= \frac{2P_{dc2}}{\hat{V}_m \cdot d_{buck,a}} \sin(\omega t) \\ i_{La1,av} &= \frac{2P_{dc1} - 4P_{dc2}}{3\hat{V}_m \cdot d_{buck,a}} \sin(\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

Similarly, when v_{am} is lower than V_{dc1} , that is, when $0 \leq t \leq t_1$ and $t_2 \leq t \leq T$, the *Boost, a1* half-bridge keeps switching, while the *Buck, a* half-bridge is clamped with S_{a1} on and S_{a2} off. To determine the duty cycle of S_{a3} , denoted as $d_{boost,a1}$, the following calculation can be

Figure 65: Key waveforms of module *a*.

Table 12: Basic equations of the proposed converter

Parameter	Equation
v_{xm}	$v_x + V_{off}$
$d_{buck,x}$	$\min(1, \frac{V_{dc1}}{v_{xm}})$
$d_{boost,x1}$	$\min(1, \frac{v_{xm}}{V_{dc1}})$
$d_{boost,a2}$	$\frac{\min(v_{am}, V_{dc1})}{V_{dc2}}$
$i_{Lx,av}$	$\frac{i_x}{d_{buck,x}}$
$i_{La1,av}$	$\frac{2P_{dc1} - 4P_{dc2}}{3\hat{V}_m \cdot d_{buck,a}} \sin(\omega t)$
$i_{La2,av}$	$\frac{2P_{dc2}}{\hat{V}_m \cdot d_{buck,a}} \sin(\omega t)$

applied:

$$d_{boost,a1} = \frac{v_{am}}{V_{dc1}} = \frac{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{off}}{V_{dc1}} \quad (55)$$

For the *Boost a2* half-bridge, $d_{boost,a2}$, can be calculated as follows:

$$d_{boost,a2} = \frac{v_{am}}{V_{dc2}} = \frac{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{off}}{V_{dc2}} \quad (56)$$

Using (54) and given that $d_{buck,a} = 1$ in this mode, $i_{La2,av}$ and $i_{La1,av}$ can be determined as:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{La2,av} &= \frac{2P_{dc2}}{\hat{V}_m} \sin(\omega t) \\ i_{La1,av} &= \frac{2P_{dc1} - 4P_{dc2}}{3\hat{V}_m} \sin(\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

The key waveforms for module a of the proposed converter are plotted in Fig. 65. Additionally, the basic characteristic equations of the proposed converters are summarized in Table 12 where $x = (a, b, c)$.

7.3 Simulation results

Simulation results of the proposed converter are presented in this section to showcase its performance under different operating conditions, where the power delivered to V_{dc1} is fixed for all tests at 6 kW. The simulations are conducted with the rated voltage at the ac port, while the dc MGs are allowed to have up to a 10% voltage deviation from their rated

Table 13: Parameters of the proposed converter

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated ac power	$P_{ac,r}$	9 kW
Rated dc power	$P_{dc1,r}, P_{dc2,r}$	6 kW, 3 kW
ac line voltage, frequency	V_{ll}, f_o	400 V, 50 Hz
dc voltage	V_{dc1}, V_{dc2}	360 – 440 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz
Inductance	L_1, L_2	330 μ H

value. Therefore, in the following simulations, V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} are set equal to 400 V and 440 V, respectively. The converter's specifications are summarized in Table 13.

Three different operating conditions are presented in this section. In the first operating condition, demonstrated in Fig. 66, the AY-MPC is controlled to deliver no power to V_{dc2} (i.e., P_{dc2} equal to zero). In this case, the converter operates as the conventional two-port Y-converter with zero average current flowing in L_2 (only a high-frequency ripple current) while i_{La1} , i_{Lb1} , and i_{Lc1} remain symmetric.

In Fig. 67, the second operating condition is presented, where P_{dc2} is equal to 1 kW. In this case, i_{La2} is controlled to deliver the required P_{dc2} , while i_{La1} is controlled to maintain balanced ac grid currents. Therefore, i_{La1} , i_{Lb1} , and i_{Lc1} are no longer symmetric, as i_{La1} has a lower amplitude, resulting in a reduced power contribution from module a to P_{dc1} compared to the remaining modules. Despite the asymmetric power flow in the AY-MPC, the ac grid currents remain sinusoidal and balanced, as evident from the simulation results.

Fig. 68 illustrates the third operating condition where P_{dc2} is equal to 3 kW, representing 50% of P_{dc1} . In this case, and as evident from (54) and (57), $i_{La1,av}$ will be zero to maintain balanced ac grid currents. Here, P_{dc1} is divided equally between module b and module c , while module a delivers only P_{dc2} . Once again as evident from the simulation results, the ac grid currents remain sinusoidal and balanced, despite the asymmetric power flow.

7.4 Experimental results

In this section, preliminary results collected from the experimental prototype are reported. A detailed discussion of the experimental prototype and various results under different operating conditions are planned to be included in the second deliverable of WP3 (D3.2).

The experimental prototype of the AY-MPC, shown in Fig. 60, is utilized to validate the converter's operation and to confirm the correctness of the presented waveforms. The proposed converter is constructed using four Imperix SIC power modules (PEB8024 with C2M0080120D SiC MOSFETs) for the boost half-bridges and three half-bridges with UF4SC120023K4S SiC MOSFETs. The converter is controlled by a B-box controller from Imperix. Bidirectional ac and dc power supplies are used to emulate the ac grid and dc mi-

Figure 66: Simulation results of the proposed converter at P_{dc1} is equal to 6 kW and P_{dc2} is equal to 0 kW.

Figure 67: Simulation results of the proposed converter at P_{dc1} is equal to 6 kW and P_{dc2} is equal to 1 kW.

Figure 68: Simulation results of the proposed converter at P_{dc1} is equal to 6 kW and P_{dc2} is equal to 3 kW.

Figure 69: Experimental waveforms in rectification mode.

crogrids. Additionally, a single-stage input filter is realized with $L_f = 1.2 \text{ mH}$ and $C_f = 10 \mu\text{F}$, while $330 \mu\text{H}$ inductors are used for L_1 and L_2 .

Experimental waveforms at steady-state are displayed in Fig. 69, where the converter operates with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 360V and 400V, respectively, and P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} equal to 2.7kW and 0.5kW, respectively. The captured waveforms encompass the ac grid voltages (v_a, v_b, v_c), ac-side voltage of module a (v_{am}), the ac grid currents (i_a, i_b, i_c), and the module a inductors' currents (i_{La1}, i_{La2}). As evident from the waveforms, the experimental waveforms match the analysis and simulation results. Additionally, the ac currents are sinusoidal, balanced, and synchronized with the ac voltages.

8 Non linear Control of the Four-wire Y-converter based on the Sliding Mode (SM) Loss-Free Resistor (LFR)

8.1 Introduction

The electrical architecture of power processing systems can be modeled using three ideal canonical elements: 1) the transformer, 2) the gyrator, and 3) the loss free resistor (LFR). These elements can be considered as a transducer with two ports, and belong to a class of ideal circuits called POPI (Power Output = Power Input) which virtually transmit the absorbed power to the output in such a way that no loss occurs.

The notion of LFR was introduced for the first time by SINGER in 1990 [157] (Fig. 70), and it consists to replace the classic resistance with an element having the same resistive characteristics, but which is not dissipative. Initially, this notion was applied only for certain power converters operating in discontinuous conduction mode (DCM) and exhibiting a resistive input impedance in steady-state [158]. Later, the concept of the LFR was used in the design of feedback controllers to obtain switching converter with resistive input impedance [159–163]. This concept is translated by the fact that input current is proportional to the input voltage and power absorbed in the input is totally transferred to the output. The LFR circuit is described by the following equations :

$$V_{in} = rI_{in} \quad (58)$$

$$V_{in}I_{in} = V_{out}I_{out} \quad (59)$$

where V_{in} , I_{in} , V_{out} , and I_{out} are the *rms* steady-state averaged values of input and output voltages and currents respectively. r is the emulated input resistive impedance, under steady state.

The synthesis of LFR obviously requires a control law to impose equation (58) on the switching converter input port. This is indeed possible in practice through an appropriate control loop.

Due to its switched nature, the power converter is considered a variable structure system

Figure 70: A circuit of LFR.

Figure 71: Block diagram of switching converter emulated as LFR in SMC.

(VSS). Therefore the good and appropriated control for this system is well-known techniques of sliding mode control (SMC) [164]. SMC has been widely used and successfully applied in DC-DC converters [165–168]. The main advantages of SMC are robustness, good dynamic response, and low implementation cost. The block diagram of a switching converter behaving as a LFR under SMC is depicted in Fig. (71) [169]. The sliding surface that imposes the input current of the converter is proportional to the voltage is described by the following switching function:

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{V_{in}}{r} - I_{in} \tag{60}$$

In steady state, when the sliding surface is reached ($\sigma(x) = 0$), the input current follows the input voltage as in (61).

$$I_{in} = \frac{V_{in}}{r} \tag{61}$$

8.2 Analysis of the Y-Converter as LFR in SMC

The Y-converter, shown in Fig. 72a, is a three-phase four-wire rectifier and is made up of three single-phase modules connected in a star configuration. Each module is an AC-DC four-switch buck-boost converter as shown in Fig. 72b. By considering each module as a POPI circuit, Y-converter can be modeled by the tetra-port circuit (Fig. 73-a). SMC can be used to impose a LFR behavior to the Y-converter by emulating each module as a resistance to its respective input phase voltage (Fig 73-b). All the power absorbed by these resistances are transmitted to the output port without losses.

$$P_{in} = P_a + P_b + P_c = P_{out} \tag{62}$$

Figure 72: The four-wire Y-converter.

Since Y-converter is a symmetric and balanced system and the modules operate independently, the power delivered by each module is defined as

$$P_a = P_b = P_c = \frac{P_{out}}{3} \tag{63}$$

From equation(63), the emulated input resistive impedance for each module is given by:

$$r_{a,b,c} = \frac{3V_{rms}^2}{P_{out}} \tag{64}$$

where V_{rms} is *rms* AC grid voltage. To provide a clear and simplified analysis, a single-module i.e., phase A analysis is provided, which can be extended similarly to the other phases.

8.3 Ideal Sliding Dynamics

Four-switch buck-boost consists of two converters = in series. Therefore, there are two basic operating modes, buck mode and boost mode. To impose a LFR behavior to both operation modes, two sliding control laws are designed, one per each mode. The goal of each controller is to force the current i_a to be sinusoidal and in phase with the AC supply voltage v_a . In each operation mode, the current i_a is controlled through the control of current inductor

Figure 73: Y-converter emulated as LFR: a) Tetra-port circuit, b) LFR circuits

\dot{i}_{La} .

8.3.1 Buck Mode

When v_{am} is greater than V_{dc} , module a works in the buck mode in which S_{a3} is kept *ON* and S_{a4} is kept *OFF* as is depicted in Fig. 74a. Assuming that the switches, inductance L and capacitors are considered ideals and applying *Kirchhoff's Law*, module a can be represented by the following switched model

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{di_a}{dt} &= \frac{v_{am}}{L_f} - \frac{v_{Cfa}}{L_f} - \frac{r_{Lf}}{L_f} i_a \\ \frac{dv_{Cfa}}{dt} &= \frac{i_a}{C_f} - \frac{i_{La}}{C_f} u_{buck,a} \\ \frac{di_{La}}{dt} &= \frac{v_{Cfa}}{L} u_{buck,a} - \frac{V_{dc}}{L} \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

where $u_{buck,a} = \{0, 1\}$ is the control signal.

In buck mode $i_a = \alpha i_{La}$ ($\alpha = \frac{V_{dc}}{v_{Cfa}}$ conversion ratio). Therefore, to force the system behaves like LFR, the sliding surface is chosen as follows:

$$\sigma_{buck,a}(x) = \left(\frac{v_{Cfa}}{r_a} - I_{off} \right) \frac{v_{Cfa}}{V_{dc}} - i_{La} \quad (66)$$

where $x = [i_a, v_{Cfa}, i_{La}]^T$ is the vector of state variables $I_{off} = \frac{V_{dc}}{r_a}$ is an offset current.

Figure 74: Operation modes of one module of the proposed converter include current paths in both buck and boost modes.

Applying the invariance conditions ($\sigma_{buck,a} = 0$ and $\dot{\sigma}_{buck,a} = 0$), the equivalent continuous control $d_{buck,a}$ can be expressed as follows:

$$d_{buck,a} = \frac{L}{r_a V_{dc}} \left(2 - \frac{V_{dc}}{v_{Cfa}} \right) \frac{dv_{Cfa}}{dt} + \frac{V_{dc}}{v_{Cfa}} \quad (67)$$

$d_{buck,a}$ represents the control law which describes the system behavior on the switching surface, where the sliding mode is reached. Thus, $d_{buck,a}$ is bounded by the maximum (=1) and minimum (=0) values of $u_{buck,a}$. To ensure that $d_{buck,a}$ is bounded between 0 and 1, it needs to see how the first term $\gamma_{buck,a} = \frac{L}{r_a V_{dc}} \left(2 - \frac{V_{dc}}{v_{Cfa}} \right) \frac{dv_{Cfa}}{dt}$ can affect $d_{buck,a}$. Fig. 75 depicts $d_{buck,a}$ without and with $\gamma_{buck,a}$. It can be seen that the term effect is negligible and the equivalent control does not exceed its limits. Therefore $d_{buck,a}$ can be defined as

$$d_{buck,a} \approx \frac{V_{dc}}{v_{Cfa}} \quad (68)$$

Substituting $u_{buck,a}$ by $d_{buck,a}$ in (65) and taking into account the restriction ($i_{La} = \frac{v_a}{r_a} \frac{v_{Cfa}}{V_{dc}}$) imposed by $\sigma_{buck,a} = 0$, the following ideal sliding-mode model is obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{di_a}{dt} &= -\frac{r_{Lf}}{L_f} i_a - \frac{v_{Cfa}}{L_f} + \frac{v_{am}}{L_f} \\ \frac{dv_{Cfa}}{dt} &= \frac{i_a}{C_f} - \frac{v_{Cfa}}{r_a C_f} + \frac{V_{dc}}{r_a C_f} \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

Figure 75: Equivalent continuous control en Buck mode for $L = 0.25 \text{ mH}$.

It can be note that due to the constraint imposed by the sliding control, the system dynamics are governed by a reduced-order model.

Using (69) and taking into account the constraint $\sigma_{buck,a} = 0$, the equilibrium point of the system is expressed as follows

$$X^* = [I_a^*, V_{Cfa}^*, I_{La}^*]^T = \left[\frac{v_a}{r_a + r_{Lf}}, v_{am} - r_{Lf} I_a^*, \frac{V_{Cfa}^*}{V_{dc}} I_a^* \right]^T \quad (70)$$

Considering that r_{Lf} is negligible, it can easily find that the power balance equation (71) is verified and the system, under SMC, behaves like LFR with a resistance r_a .

$$P_{in} = \langle i_a^* V_{Cfa}^* \rangle = \langle I_{dc} V_{dc} \rangle = \langle I_{La}^* V_{dc} \rangle = P_{out} = \frac{V_{a,rms}^2}{r_a} \quad (71)$$

In order to study the stability of the system, the Laplace transform is applied on (69) in order to obtain to obtain the transfer function $\frac{V_{Cfa}(s)}{V_{am}(s)}$. The resulting characteristic equation (72) corresponds to a stable system.

$$L_f C_f s^2 + L_f C_f \left(\frac{r_{Lf}}{L_f} + \frac{1}{r_a C_f} \right) s + 1 = 0 \quad (72)$$

8.3.2 Boost Mode

When v_{am} is less than V_{dc} , module a works in the boost mode in which S_{a1} is kept *ON* and S_{a2} is kept *OFF* as is depicted in Fig. 74b. Assuming that the switches, inductance L and capacitors are ideal and applying *Kirchhoff's* Law, module a can be represented by the

following switched model:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{di_a}{dt} &= \frac{v_{am}}{L_f} - \frac{v_{Cfa}}{L_f} - \frac{r_{L_f}i_a}{L_f} \\ \frac{dv_{Cfa}}{dt} &= \frac{i_a}{C_f} - \frac{i_{La}}{C_f} \\ \frac{di_{La}}{dt} &= \frac{v_{Cfa}}{L} - \frac{V_{dc}}{L}u_{boost,a} \end{aligned} \tag{73}$$

where $u_{boost,a} = \{0, 1\}$ is the control signal. The same procedure as in the case of buck mode will be applied to design the control law.

In the boost mode $i_a = i_{La}$. Therefore, the sliding surface that forces the system behaves like LFR is defined as :

$$\sigma_{boost,a}(x) = \left(\frac{v_{Cfa}}{r_a} - I_{off}\right) - i_{La} \tag{74}$$

where $x = [i_a, v_{Cfa}, i_{La}]^T$ is the vector of state variables $I_{off} = \frac{V_{dc}}{r_a}$ is an offset current.

Applying the invariance conditions ($\sigma_{boost,a} = 0$ and $\dot{\sigma}_{boost,a} = 0$), the equivalent continuous control $d_{boost,a}$ (75) is obtained.

$$d_{boost,a} = -\frac{L}{r_a V_{dc}} \frac{dv_{Cfa}}{dt} + \frac{v_{Cfa}}{V_{dc}} \tag{75}$$

$d_{boost,a}$ represents the control law which describes the system behavior on the switching surface, where the sliding mode is reached. Thus, $d_{boost,a}$ is bounded by the maximum (=1) and minimum (=0) values of $u_{boost,a}$. To ensure that $d_{boost,a}$ is bounded between 0 and 1, it needs to see how the first term $\gamma_{boost,a} = -\frac{L}{r_a V_{dc}} \frac{dv_{Cfa}}{dt}$ can affect $d_{boost,a}$. Fig. 76 depicts $d_{boost,a}$ without and with $\gamma_{boost,a}$. It can be seen that the term effect is negligible and the equivalent control does not exceed its limits. Substituting $u_{boost,a}$ by $d_{boost,a}$ in (73) and

Figure 76: Equivalent continuous control en Buck mode for $L = 0.25 \text{ mH}$.

taking into account the restriction ($i_{La} = \frac{v_a}{r_a} - I_{off}$) imposed by $\sigma_{boost,a} = 0$, the following ideal sliding-mode model is obtained

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{di_a}{dt} &= -\frac{r_{Lf}}{L_f}i_a - \frac{v_{Cfa}}{L_f} + \frac{v_{am}}{L_f} \\ \frac{dv_{Cfa}}{dt} &= \frac{i_a}{C_f} - \frac{v_{Cfa}}{r_a C_f} + \frac{V_{dc}}{r_a C_f} \\ \frac{di_{La}}{dt} &= \frac{1}{r_a} \frac{dv_{Cfa}}{dt}\end{aligned}\quad (76)$$

As can be seen, due to the constraint imposed on di_{La} by (74), the system dynamics is described by linear reduced-order model.

Using (76) and taking into account the constraint $\sigma_{buck,a} = 0$, the equilibrium point of the system is expressed as follows

$$X^* = [I_a^*, V_{Cfa}^*, I_{La}^*]^T = \left[\frac{v_a}{r_a + r_{Lf}}, v_{am} - r_{Lf} I_a^*, I_a^* \right]^T \quad (77)$$

Considering that r_{Lf} is negligible, we can easily find that the power balance equation is verified (78) and the system, under SMC, behaves like LFR of resistance r_a .

$$P_{in} = \langle I_a^* V_{Cfa}^* \rangle = \langle I_{dc}^* V_{dc} \rangle = I_{La}^* \frac{V_{Cfa}^*}{V_{dc}} V_{dc} = \langle I_a^* V_{Cfa}^* \rangle = P_{out} = \frac{V_{a,rms}^2}{r_a} \quad (78)$$

In order to study the stability of the system, the Laplace transform is applied on (76) in order to obtain the transfer function $\frac{V_{Cfa}(s)}{V_{am}(s)}$. The resulting characteristic equation (79) corresponds to a stable system.

$$L_f C_f s^2 + L_f C_f \left(\frac{r_{Lf}}{L_f} + \frac{1}{r_a C_f} \right) s + 1 = 0 \quad (79)$$

8.4 Simulation Results

The converter's behavior as LFR under SMC is verified by means of numerical simulations using MATLAB/Simulink. The parameters of system are outlined in Table 14. Regarding the implementation of SMC, the hysteresis band has been taken $\pm 0.25A$. The performance of the designed controller is tested, first of all, under balanced AC grid conditions, secondly, under load transient and finally under unbalanced AC grid conditions.

8.4.1 Balanced Grid Voltage

Fig. 77 depicts the steady state response of Y-converter under nominal operating conditions. It is clear that forcing the system to behave like a LFR by means of SMC, an efficient current sharing and a good inductor reference current tracking are achieved. It can be seen that the line currents and AC grid voltages are in phase which means that a power factor close to

Table 14: Y-Converter parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Nominal power	P	7 kW
AC grid voltage	V_a	230 V
Line frequency	f	50 Hz
DC voltage	V_{dc}	400 V
Inductor	L_f, r_{Lf}	50 μ H, 0.5 Ω
Capacitor	C_f	20 μ F

unity is achieved. It should be noted that by applying this the proposed control, a very small value of the THD equal to 0.52% has been achieved. .

8.4.2 Load Transient

The transient response of the Y-converter to step change of the output power from 3 kW to 7 kW at $t = 60$ ms is depicted in Fig. 78 . The results show that the system controller demonstrated a fast and robust behavior. The AC grid currents, and the inductor currents exhibit fast response to this power change so as to track their references.

8.4.3 Unbalanced Grid Voltages

Fig. 79 shows the transient response of Y-converter under unbalanced grid voltages. The amplitudes of AC grid voltages are modified to be 230 V, 210 V, and 190 V, respectively at $t = 52$ ms. It can see that the proposed controller reacts sufficiently fast to the line voltage variations. The AC grid currents, and the inductor currents exhibit fast response to this power change so as to track their new references.

It is worth noting that a change in the output power or in AC grid voltage means a change in the power absorbed at the input port or at the output port. This power transfer operation from one port to another is controlled by the emulated input resistance r_{abc} . That is to say, when the power output or AC grid voltage changes, r_{abc} adapts itself to this change which in turn causes both grid and inductor currents to change, in order to reach the new operation point.

(a) AC grid voltages and currents waveforms.

(b) AC-side voltages and Filter capacitor voltages.

(c) Inductor currents.

Figure 77: Steady-state response of the Y-converter for 7 kW rated power.
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(a) Emulated input resistance and AC grid currents.

(b) Inductor currents.

Figure 78: Transient response of Y-converter to step change of the output power from 3 kW to 7 kW.

(a) Emulated input resistance and AC grid currents.

(b)

(c) Inductor currents.

Figure 79: Transient response of Y-converter to step change in the line voltages.
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9 Conclusions

The primary scope of Work Package 3 activities was to investigate and enable MPCs in low-voltage distribution networks, considering both distribution-level and household/residential scenarios.

For distribution networks, research challenges associated with SOP converters during abnormal conditions, such as faults and voltage sags, were studied. The behavior of SOPs was examined, and standard requirements were applied to case studies to define the converters' duties. Challenges in meeting these duties based on current state-of-the-art technologies were uncovered. To address LVRT and FRT capabilities, two approaches were proposed: unified control logic and centralized DC voltage control. The unified control logic was designed to ensure compliance with both LVRT and FRT requirements. While LVRT specifically addresses the system's response to voltage sags, FRT covers a broader range of fault conditions. The proposed approach ensures sustained connectivity during voltage sags, enhances reactive power support, and aims to improve reliability by reducing the risk of voltage collapse. This is achieved through maintaining DC voltage control even in the event of a master station failure. Various scenarios were explored, detailing the specific responses required based on the nature and characteristics of each voltage sag or fault.

A centralized DC voltage control architecture was used to prioritize the regulation of the DC bus with N ports, ensuring robustness against AC faults. DC ports with available power supply elements are prioritized; otherwise, AC ports connected to the grid control the DC bus. Under normal operation, the control was designed using a linear model and the pole placement technique. To ensure the desired dynamic response during AC faults, the reactive power control block and PLL were modified. In addition, current saturation and fault current injection mechanisms were added to the system. The fault current injection block injects reactive current to support the grid, as defined by grid codes and standards. Solutions were previously presented with balanced and unbalanced faults for systems with more than two ports. However, an FRT strategy was presented that does not depend on fault location, due to the design of the centralized DC bus voltage controller. FRT capabilities are ensured for deep faults on ports, except when a deep fault affects all AC ports, in which case the DC bus voltage cannot be controlled due to the unavailability of active power from the ports.

To analyze and prevent the destabilizing impact of multi-port interlinking converters in grid-connecting scenarios with arbitrary, even meshed, termination (grid impedance), an unterminated all-port MIMO admittance passivity-oriented controller design framework was presented. This was exemplified through a buck converter with a digital current-control system. The impact of the control loop's crossover frequency and overall delay on its

MIMO admittance passivity properties was illustrated, showing that higher values of these parameters worsen passivity properties. Two techniques for enhancing a converter's all-port MIMO admittance passivity—active damping impedance emulation and multi-sampled pulse-width modulation—were investigated and shown to be effective. Both frequency and time domain validations of the presented methodology were performed using control-hardware-in-the-loop simulations. Experimental validation will be addressed in the future.

For residential applications, two novel single-stage non-isolated MPCs were proposed to interface the three-phase AC grid with DC systems. These MPCs enable direct power sharing between DC systems, minimizing dependence on the AC grid and enhancing the efficiency and power density of the power electronic interface compared to multiple two-port converters. The proposed converters provide single-stage power conversion across different ports, potentially leading to higher efficiency and power density. Furthermore, the absence of bulky intermediate DC-link capacitors and transformers in the proposed topology contributes to improved power density and reduced costs. Additionally, the proposed MPCs feature buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports, independent of the DC ports' voltage, providing flexibility to directly interface with a wide range of DC systems.

The proposed converters build upon the two-port Y-converter, transforming it from a two-port configuration into a multi-port one capable of connecting multiple DC systems to a three-phase AC grid. In its original form, the two-port Y-converter comprised three four-switch buck-boost modules. To develop the multi-port converter, the four-switch buck-boost converter was expanded into a six-switch buck-boost converter formed with a shared buck half-bridge and two boost half-bridges, which can be configured symmetrically or asymmetrically. In the symmetric configuration, the extension from a four-switch to a six-switch buck-boost converter is applied to all three modules. In the asymmetric configuration, the extension is applied only to one of the modules.

The asymmetric multi-port Y-converter offers a reduced structure with fewer semiconductor devices and inductors compared to the symmetric multi-port Y-converter (Y-MPC). For the case study where the two DC systems have different power levels, the AY-MPC enables the integration of the lower-power DC system into the three-phase AC grid with a minimum number of components, resulting in a simpler structure and compact size. However, a challenge with the AY-MPC is to maintain balanced AC-grid currents.

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